

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

D2.2 European Rural Bioeconomy Network creation and stakeholders mapping (1st update)

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Executive Summary

This document is the update of the D2.1 report on status of engagement of key actors in the project countries and the status of liaison with other EU projects. It corresponds to the status at M24, and will be followed by a last update in M36 (D2.3).

This document follows same structure as D2.1 and thus has been divided into three parts according to three “areas of action” or domains, where the engagement of key actors and liaison actions with projects and networks have to take place in order to connect project actions with the key actors and targeted actors. Under the perspective of BioRural strategy these actions are crucial to support the implementation and impact of BioRural actions, as well as to grow-up a ERBN community to persist after project ends.

Area of action #1 - National & subnational (section#2)

The final aim of BioRural is to promote the up-scale in the adoption of small scale bio-based solutions applicable in rural areas. Under this document “Key actors” are those organisations, companies, public bodies or persons considered crucial to either: (a) support and implement BioRural actions, or (b) support the establishment of an operational European Rural Bioeconomy Network - ERBN. BioRural operates in 14 EU countries, and as well at EU level. In order to achieve a good engagement of key actors BioRural partners have performed a coordinated action of rapprochement from the project start, and reported it at M12 in D2.1, and now at M24 in D2.2. The results of direct engagement with key actors are presented in Section 2 of this document.

As result of the engagement it has been possible to achieve next indicators:

- The coordination and reporting of the status of engagement has been organised by geographical areas called RBP (Rural Bioeconomy Platforms) as it was already arranged in D2.1
- At the current reporting in M24 partners have reported to have identified a total of 1,131 key actors potentially relevant to implement and support BioRural or for an effective uptake of project results. This implies 244 new key actors, in respect the 887 actors identified in M12(under D2.1)
- A total of 824 key actors have been communicated, 542 of them by meetings (290 e-meetings, calls, direct meetings) more than at M12
- This initial rapprochement has led to 356 key actors (30% of the 1,131 identified) to already participate in project actions, 190 more than at M12
- A total of 229 key actors (20% of the 1,131 identified) have gone further and not just participated, but collaborated with BioRural (co-organising event, supporting workshops preparation, reporting success cases, etc.) 151 more than at M12.
- A total of 472 persons are now part of ERBN, 338 being affiliated to key actors organisations identified, whereas 134 are from other stakeholders (not key actors to implement BioRural or ERBN, but individuals, companies, organisations interested and recipients of project results). This achievement is larger than the target set by M24 of 280 members. Membership has been reached mainly by subscriptions through the BioRural toolkit (432).

Section #2 presents details of these achievements aggregated by each geographical RBP (SW, SE, NW, NE). The individual country updates are presented as an Appendix to this deliverable.

Area of action #2 – Bioeconomy Networks and projects (section #3)

Under this area, two main results are described: (1) the status of RBA - Rural Bioeconomy Alliance and (2) the status of connection and collaboration with EU and national projects, and (3) the status of connection and collaboration with EU and national networks.

Rural Bioeconomy Alliance - RBA (section 3.2)

This cluster of EU-funded bioeconomy projects was created and launched on May 2023 (Month M9). The RBA is a platform to strengthen the collaboration and impacts of individual EU projects on bioeconomy devoted to small

scale solutions and rural areas. It was founded among 11 EU funded projects. At month M24 a total of 29 individual collaborations took effect between partners of BioRural and RBA projects, thus connecting and reinforcing BioRural and the 11 RBA projects.

Liaison with national and EU projects (section 3.3)

The second sub-action line is the individual liaison of BioRural partners with EU and national projects.

A total of three long term EU initiatives have been identified: EU-Farmbook, modernAKIS and Tools4CAP. The main synergy has taken place with EU-Farmbook including a collaboration and an agreement to connect BioRural toolkit with EU-Farmbook.

Partners have identified at M24 a total of 24 EU project and 8 national projects to establish synergies with. About EU projects, a total of 48 lines of collaboration were discussed, achieving 29 collaborations taking place already by M24. In respect the national funded projects, a total of 8 (2 more than at M12) have been identified. From the 17 potential lines of collaboration, a total of 9 synergies occurred by M24.

Liaison with national and EU Networks (section 3.4)

In respect to CAP Networks, at M24 the EU CAP network has already contacted and object of short collaboration on purpose of T1.2. Notwithstanding more contacts are expected in the last stage of the project. In respect the National CAP Networks 9 of them were contacted by M12, now being 2 more totalling 11 out of the 14 BioRural countries. Several synergies took place to disseminate BioRural actions like workshops, through their channels. As well several partners maintain a regular contact, thus allowing mutual transfer of info, more than specific synergies.

Liaison with other EU and national networks has proceeded from M12, when 6 EU and 18 national networks had been identified, 8 of them with synergies under discussion. At M24 partners have achieved:

- EU referential sectorial non-bioeconomy networks: Synergies have occurred with Bioenergy Europe as speaker in BioRural online tutorials, with the ICA - Association for European Life Science Universities to promote the EU Challenge or with ERIAFF - European Regions for Innovation in Agriculture, Food and Forestry to disseminate BioRural.
- EU bioeconomy networks: 8 have been identified. Among them 5 have been contacted, and 6 individual collaborations took place from M12 till M24 with the Community of Practice for Bioeconomy Education in Europe (ICA-CoP Bio-Edu), Biorefine Cluster Europe, ERDN - European Rural Development Network and the CIGR Bioeconomy Network.
- National networks (both bioeconomy and others): a total of 21 have been identified by M24, 5 more than at M12. From the total 23 synergies identified, a total of 20 individual collaborations have been triggered with 15 of these networks.

Area of action #3 – ERBN internal structure (section #4)

The third Area of action for the ERBN strategy is the creation of the internal structure of organisations to take over the management of the network after BioRural finishes. At M12 partners agreed to build a management structure with key actors interested to steer and manage the ERBN. D2.1 included in section #4 the summary of challenges and recommendations to build the structure, a governance map based on EU regional geographic platforms (RBPs) and a plan of actions to build it during M13-M24 and M25-M36 periods.

It has been found by BioRural partners that the best option to keep value is to keep ERBN specific and thematic. Several partners, and potentially external key actors, would be eager to be part of a ERBN management structure after BioRural finishes, if the network is thematic. It would allow a partner with specific interests in bioenergy, for example, to be part of the Bioenergy board of the network.

Accordingly a new governance structure has been drafted. And the planning to create a core structure has shifted, to take place in third projects' year (M25-M36). During this second year (M13-M24) the efforts have been placed to define the new orientation of the network, and the strategy to settle it and keep it alive after BioRural finishes. Partners have started connections to link the ERBN it with key structures like EU-Farmbook and modernAKIS. And have as well analysed the current status and proposed measures to dynamise the interactions between the ERBN members.

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1 Introduction

1.1 About this document

The aim of BioRural is to establish a European network of rural Bioeconomy stakeholders by:

- developing 4 regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBP) in a geographic context, to connect neighbouring countries and identify commonalities, stimulate knowledge exchange, cooperation and collaboration and assist on developing future rural Bioeconomy initiatives.
- liaising with Bioeconomy networks and projects, to further support the knowledge transfer and the impact and reach of BioRural, by identifying synergies and agreeing upon formal collaborations

BioRural works parallel in 14 countries, and has established a structure of organization internally dividing the actions in 4 EU geo-regions, called RBP: Rural bioeconomy Platforms, as depicted below in Figure 1.

Figure 1. BioRural and regional organization into geographic RBPs

The final end of both BioRural and its structures, the ERBN and the regional RBPs, is bringing together local and regional rural stakeholders for the development of a local circular economy, supporting long term sustainable local economic prospects that indirectly support also the wider local economy.

For that purpose, BioRural partners set a strategy devoted to engage key actors, who are the able to trigger or multiply effects of the final targeted actors, the potential adopters of bioeconomy innovations on circularity applicable by local stakeholders in rural areas. Thus they were arranged as next:

- **Key actors:** those who (1) Perform transfer to or influence targeted actors, and/or (2) may facilitate project implementation and widen project impacts. Examples: Farmers or foresters organisations, clusters, consultants, universities, research, extension services, networks, projects, technology facilitators, etc.
 - ➔ BioRural aims to engage them, to participate in project actions and to collaborate to widen project impact. They are object of tracking (section #2)
- **Targeted actors:** those who are potential adopters of new small-scale biobased solutions. Examples: Farmers, foresters, rural SMEs, local industries, investors, local government.

→ BioRural aims to increase awareness and readiness for adoption of biobased innovations

At Month 12 (end august 2023) BioRural submitted D2.1, which describe the methodology followed to perform a coordinated work in the key actors engagement, in the liaison with strategic projects and networks, and in the consolidation of a potential management structure for the ERBN. The present document builds on D2.1, and focuses to update the current status at M24, and report principal highlights achieved.

1.2 Structure of the document

Following the structure of D2.1, the present document is as well arranged according to the three areas of action covered by T2.1 and T2.2:

- #1: National & subnational (requiring contact with key actors) aiming at incorporating key actors to BioRural actions and set a community of interest of the ERBN
- #2: Bioeconomy networks and projects (specially allowing knowledge transfer) allowing to multiply effects and obtain support for both BioRural actions and ERBN
- #3: Internal structure able to manage and maintain the ERBN structure and growth

These areas of action are briefly summarized into Figure 2 (more details in Section 1.2 in previous deliverable D2.1).

Figure 2. BioRural and ERBN: the three areas of action to set the strategies

2 Area of action #1: key actors and stakeholders at national level

2.1 Introduction

This section #2 updates the status of key actors engagement and ERBN community status previously reported in Deliverable report D2.1 in August 2023 (M12). The first version included a description of the methodology followed, the materials and templates utilised, and the status of key actors activation achieved by M12. We refer to D2.1 Sections 2.1.

Notwithstanding it is precise to include again here the definition of tags, which are necessary for a good interpretation of the graphs and tables presented next in section 2.2. Table 1 describes the tags describing key actors main profile, whereas Table 2 describes the bioeconomy themes that a key actor may fall into.

Table 1. Tags utilized in BioRural to classify the key actor profile

#TAG	TAGS for Stakeholder <u>profiles</u>
#PP	Primary producers (individual farmers, foresters, fishers)
#PP.Org	Primary producers organisations
#Comp	Company, SME, self-employed (not being primary producer)
#Comp.Org	Sectorial, SMEs, company organisations
#Cons	Consultant (private, in any field. Profile can be specified with the Bioeconomy theme #TAG)
#Cons.Org	Consultants organisations
#RU	Rural actor (relevant for project as single stakeholder: city council, county board, local leader, etc.)
#RU.Org	Rural organisations (rural development, Local Action Groups, rural territories, etc.)
#Gov	Government department, service, etc.
#R/Ed	Research and/or education (universities, research centres, tech. centres, schools, vocational schools, etc.)
#Net	Network (type can be specified with Bioeconomy #TAGs and in comments)
#Proj	Project (type can be specified with Bioeconomy theme #TAGs and in comments)
#Oth	Any other not falling in previous (civil organisations, etc.)

Table 2. Tags utilized in BioRural to classify the key actors themes of bioeconomy

#TAG	TAGs for bioeconomy <u>theme</u>
#Agr/F	Agri/Food: Related to agriculture and food (inland resources)
#For	Forest: Related to forest (inland resources)
#Aq	Aquatic: Related to fisheries and aquiculture (aquatic resources)
#BE	Bioenergy: Transforming bio-resource into energy, or providing services or good to this value chain
#BM	Biomaterials: Transforming bio-resource into intermediate or final bio-based products and goods, or providing services or good to this value chain
#Hor	Horizontal: Any actor like rural organisations, large R&D centres, which are not theme-specific and cover all 5 bioeconomy classes
#Nspec	Non-specific. As could be an innovation booster. May cover some areas, not being specific of any of them.

2.2 SW RBP Results – Status at M24

2.2.1 SW RBP Overview

The BioRural South-West Rural Bioeconomy Platform (SW RBP) is built by 3 countries: Spain, Italy and Portugal. Among them, Spain behaves internally as head of the RBP, adopting the role of RBP leader. Each country developed a specific strategy for key actors engagement at M12, which can be consulted as an Annex to D2.1.

In the present summary the aggregated figures of SW RBP are presented, with specific insights to individual country highlights at the end of this sub-section.

SW RBP: Key actors profile in the strategy

BioRural partners performed by M12 individual analysis by country, to identify which key actors would be relevant for supporting BioRural actions in their own country, and to engage to participate, collaborate and become part of the community of the European Rural Bioeconomy Network.

The analysis led to each BioRural country to elaborate by M12 a list of key actors, including the organisation profile, key bioeconomy topics and relevance for the project. As the project advanced after M12, partners have detected additional key actors who had not been considered at the initial moment. The status of identified key actors at M24 is presented next in Figure 3 arranged by profiles. Additionally Table 3 indicates the KPIs planned in general for the whole project, showing key actors profiles and the bioeconomy topics of interest.

Figure 3. SW RBP: summary of identified key actors profiles by M24

In respect M12, at M24 a total of new additional 25 key actors have been added to the identified key actors considered as potentially relevant to support BioRural actions and widen project impacts. As observed in Figure 3, at M24 the total key actors identified add **233 organisations in the 3 RBP countries**. As observed the predominant profile is research and education organisations (65) as well as companies, clusters and sectorial organisations (42). Primary producers (31) and government bodies (33) are also a noticeable part of the share. Rural organisations and consultants, who may take a role of facilitators for dissemination (complementing primary producers organisations), add 13 and 11 organisations respectively. A total of 20 Networks and 10 Projects have been identified as relevant for the project in the SW RBP. In respect the distribution of key actors identified at M12, the share is similar, with an increase of companies and companies organisations.

In respect the bioeconomy topics covered by these key actors, they are presented in Table 3. The distribution is quite similar as that reported at M12. The new actors added to the list of key actors targeted have been distributed evenly among topics, resulting in a similar percentual distribution, with changes of barely 1 or 2 percentiles. The prevailing classes are the inland resources, Agri-Food (#Agr/F) and Forest (#For) with percentages of 19 and 18%. Rest of bioeconomy themes like Aquatic resources (#Aq), Bioenergy (#BE) and Biomaterials (#BM) all get good shares above 12%. The distribution is therefore well balanced, specially taking into account the fact that #hor and

non specific (#Nspec) key actors add in total 69 organisations (23%). In this later #Hor group multiple research centres and rural organisations are included, therefore being connected to all or most of 5 bioeconomy areas.

Table 3. SW RBP: Bioeconomy themes and strategy KPIs as planned at M24 of project

Period: M1-M36 Bioeconomy theme	TOTAL		Nr. By profile								
	Nr	%	#PP or #PPOrg	#Comp or #Comp.Org	#Cons or #Cons.Org	#RU or #RU.Org	#Gov	#R/Ed	#Net	#Proj	#Oth
[Agr/F] Agri/F	55	19%	15	8	4	0	8	14	4	2	0
[For] Forest	54	18%	11	3	4	0	10	17	4	3	2
[Aq] Aquatic	37	12%	10	6	1	0	8	6	5	1	0
[BE] Bioenergy	44	15%	0	14	2	1	6	10	1	3	7
[BM] Biomaterials	38	13%	0	11	1	0	3	14	3	3	3
[Hor] Horizontal	54	18%	0	4	1	12	11	17	5	3	1
[Nspec] Non specific	15	5%	0	3	5	0	2	5	0	0	0
TOTAL (Nr)	297	100%	36	49	18	13	48	83	22	15	13
TOTAL (%)	100%	100%	12%	16%	6%	4%	16%	28%	7%	5%	4%

IMPORTANT NOTE: this table summarises the tags, to identify if all bioeconomy themes are being covered in the strategy to approach key actors. Since several key actors have been tagged with more than one tag, the total accounting of tags (297) is larger than the total number of key actors (233).

RBP SW: Status at M24 (August 2024)

Activation of the key actors started by carrying out communications and meetings. During this first stage, **by end of August 2023** (Month 12 of project) the **SW RBP partners considered more relevant initially 119 out of the 208 key actors identified**. After this initial stage, it is considered the rest of actors may be object of approach as the diverse BioRural key actions or key stages take place. Therefore, the whole set of actors identified (233) are in principle potentially targeted in the period M12-M24.

As observed in Table 4, a total of 182 **actors have been object of communication** leading to a total of 107 meetings. These communications have triggered **the effect of 76 key actors having already either participated** (as audience by attending events, meetings, workshops) **or collaborated** (by supporting project, as by providing data, vision, connecting with other actors, or co-organising workshops or events), **or both of them, adding 60 participations and 88 collaborations**.

From the **233 key actors identified, 51 remain at the moment inactive** and not aware of the project (at least there is no evidence of their awareness and interest).

Table 4. SW RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M24

ACTIONS	Nr. KEY ACTORS		TOTAL NR of actions		Interpretation (figures at M24)
	M12	M24	M12	M24	
Communications	100	182	100	182	Communications are informative or "ice-breaking" contacts performed to make aware of BioRural exists, and its aims. But they are not engagement actions. <i>A total of 182 key actors have been object of communication with either emails or calls.</i>
Meetings	44	78	55	107	<u>Meetings are direct actions of engagement</u> (visits, in person talk, phone or e-meetings) where partners explain value and try to activate interest, so that key actors will take part into BioRural actions. <i>A total of 78 key actors approached, few of them with more than one meeting, totalling 107 meetings.</i>
Participations	12	46	13	60	<u>Participation refers to</u> take part in a project action, meaning key actors is active, but not meaning they are supporting project actions. Examples are: participate as audience in a seminar or workshop, respond a survey, etc.

					A total of 46 key actors have participated in BioRural actions by M24. Several of them participated in more than one action (adding a total of 60 participations). Among these 46 key actors, 24 of them have also collaborated, meaning that 22 can be considered active, but not still engaged (see Figure 4).
Collaborations	24	54	30	88	<u>Collaboration means</u> that engagement has been successful to trigger key actors to support BioRural actions: by collaborating in organising a workshop, by engaging other stakeholders to participate in project surveys, etc. A total of 54 key actors have collaborated with BioRural. Several of them collaborated not just once, and therefore 88 collaborations took place.

As observed in the period M12 to M24 the increase of meetings have doubled. This is an indicator of the interaction that SW RBP partners have had with the key actors in their countries. These meetings have been on purpose of not only providing information, but to invite to actions or to obtain support to cooperate. As a result the participations and collaborations have taken off: from 12 key actors participating in M12 to 46 doing it by M24, and from 24 key actors having collaborated by M12, up to 54 in M24. In total 60 participations and 88 collaborations have been counted, an outstanding evolution from M12. The fact is that from M12 till M24 partners had the mission to organise workshops, events, or the SW call for the EU Challenge; as well partners had to contribute to the contents of the BioRural toolkit. For that the participation and collaboration of key actors was crucial. And the fact they did participate and collaborate is a great indicator that BioRural is being connected with the targeted key actors.

These figures are also displayed visually and disaggregated in Figure 4 by key actor profile. It is evidenced that the actors more prone to participate are Research Organisations

Figure 4. SW RBP: status of activation of key actors at M24 LEFT: Targeted VS Achieved contacts. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor

As observed in Figure 4 (left) during the period M12-M24 the SW RBP partners faced to potentially contact and or engage the whole set of identified key actors (totalling 233). Partners have finally approached (aware, active or engaged) 182 of them by M24. The remaining 51 actors identified (in each country) will be object to consideration during period M24-M36, to optimise project results. This may lead to realise several key actors initially thought to be targeted, to not be relevant anymore, and thus to steer the strategy accordingly in collaborations with key actors already engaged and resulting strategical for the successful implementation of BioRural actions.

As relevant project actions took place several participations and collaborations were being triggered. Among the 182 key actors object of contact for awareness, a total of 76 have already participated and/or collaborated, meaning:

- 46 key actors have participated, but not collaborated; thus they reach the status of “active”

- 54 actors have collaborated, meaning they reached the status of “engaged” with BioRural. It must be noted that several of these actors, 24 in total, have done both, participate and collaborate. Notwithstanding in terms of degree of engagement they are classified with the superior stage, “engaged”.

RBP SW key actors analysis and next steps

To further identify the status of advance in the engagement of key actors, each country partner has performed an analysis to cross-check the degree of activation with the relevance that the key actors may have for project implementation and growth of ERBN in their countries. It has been analysed using the “quadrant diagram” (methodology and explanation provided in D2.1, section 2.2.2).

Figure 5 shows by RBP country the evolution of the key actors from M12 (August 2023) until M24 (August 2024).

Figure 5. SW RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M24

In respect the planning for the next period (M24 – M36), it has been agreed inside the project to continue the logical actions as next:

- 1) Concentrate in more relevant key actors to make them move towards the right-side of the graph, meaning their status of activation in respect BioRural and the ERBN improves.

Relevant and crucial key actors to be contacted to pass (at least) from...			
...inactive...		... to aware	Communication actions and meetings. Showing the value of BioRural ACTIONS
...aware...		... to active	...showing the specific actions where they can get value
...active...		... to engaged	...offering to collaborate in actions of their high interest

- 2) As project evolves continue discovering new key actors that may be interested to be object of communication, to incorporate to the tracking

Specific details and highlights by each SW RBP country is presented below.

RBP SW: ERBN and adhesion of key actors and another stakeholders

In the initial planning set by SW RBP partners, it was set a target of achieving 60 key actors to be part of the ERBN community by end of August 2024 (BioRural project Month 24). The individual minimum target was set by country to reach at least 20 organisations enrolled by the mentioned date. This enrolment can take place and can be proved by:

- persons registering into the toolkit (key actors or stakeholders organisations)
- alternatively, under reception of a formal statement (email or letter) of their intend to collaborate with BioRural and the ERBN (mostly key actors).

At month M24 the achievements are summarised into Figure 6. As observed on the left side at M24 a total of 127 members from key actors or stakeholders are considered as ERBN members. A total of 123 have subscribed to the ERBN by registering through the BioRural toolkit, whereas 4 have done it by formally agreeing to support BioRural and ERBN. This total of 123 members of the ERBN complies with the minimum target set of 60 to be reached by M24. This shows an outstanding contribution from the SE RBP in the path to start growing the ERBN community.

Among these 123 members, 72 persons belong to key actors organisations and 60 to stakeholders organisations. Stakeholders have not been object of direct communication, but have subscribed either after been aware of BioRural through communication (social media, posts, news, fairs, etc.) or after participating in any of BioRural actions (workshops, tutorials, events, etc.). This aggregation of key actors and stakeholders in connection through a platform, interested in innovation, bioeconomy and application of new small scale solutions, is a principal value which in return is expected to attract more organisations to enrol into the ERBN in the next period (by M36, August 2025).

As observed Figure 6 (right) depicts the distribution of the 127 members from SW RBP registered in the ERBN through the BioRural toolkit of by formal declaration at M24. The three principal groups are Research organisations, private companies and associations and clusters, which add a total of 116 persons, and show an even distribution. Public administrations and government add only 9 members, which talks of the difficulty to get public actors as part of these type of networks. Additionally other 3 actors fall under the classification of other.

Figure 6. SW RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M24. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile

2.2.2 Highlights by SW RBP country: Spain, Italy and Portugal

The general planning of the strategies for Spain, Italy and Portugal is available as an Annex to D2.1. Here a brief update and main highlights of the M24 status are presented.

SPAIN

At M24 the total key actors identified adds a total of 84. A total of 15 key actors have been added in the period M12-M24, as they were new success cases (reported under T2.4) or necessary collaborators for the regional workshops under T3.2 and for launching the EU Challenge (T3.3). A total of 57 key actors have been approached until M24, leading to 20 having already participated in at least one project action, and 29 of them having already collaborated, supporting BioRural implementation (e.g. as co-organiser of T3.2 workshops, or by bridging towards other organisations).

The good evolution of the involvement of key actors into project actions is well observed into Figure 5 with the quadrant graphs. It is there evident how the rightmost quadrants (meaning actors already engaged and collaborating) is more densely populated than the graph at M12. Notwithstanding the period M24 to M36 it must be reconsidered to invest efforts to involve key organisations either in project actions or into ERBN maintenance.

In respect ERBN subscription, target by M24 was initially set to 20 organisations. This figure was already surpassed at M12, with a total of 35 members adhered to ERBN community. At the current status, a total community of 45 users can be considered as part of ERBN. This shows a steady increase of ERBN subscriptions. Notwithstanding, it is evidenced that ERBN subscriptions were easier from key actors (object of direct engagement) than from individual stakeholders (who can access freely toolkit contents, but may not find added value by subscribing).

ITALY

At the end of the second year of operation of the project AIEL successfully mapped 57 key actors in all the sector of the bioeconomy covering all the bioeconomy sectors and a broad range of profiles. The activity of tracking key actor was mostly performed in the first year and in the second year only 6 key actors were added to the list and national activities mainly focused on secure and involve the already targeted actors.

The involvement of actors grows easier as long as the most relevant key actors were engaged. Active participation is nevertheless very difficult to achieve, key actors and generally stakeholders have grown weary of networks and platforms which in their experience have not been effective in the past in connecting stakeholders.

Regaining the trust of the stakeholder is a difficult and demanding process in which active support and cooperation (like co-organization and participation in workshops) is playing a crucial role.

The quadrant graph offers an explanatory view of the evolution, between the representation taken in month 12 and the one taken in month 24, the number of mapped key actors shows a minor difference but is clear that the process of activation is working and several key actors moved from inactive to activated. Even so, the majority of the actors (slightly less than 50% of the mapped actors) are in the “aware” phase, meaning that the partner engaged them and informed them about the project but it wasn’t able to activate the stakeholder. The activation of the already contacted stakeholders will be a crucial activity from M24 to M36.

Regarding all the stakeholder either key actors or not the country abundantly fulfil the target for the period, achieving the subscription of 51 members in the ERBN (given a target of 25).

PORTUGAL

At Month 24 (M24), Portugal identified 97 key actors, with 9 new additions from M12-M24, primarily companies, research institutions, governmental services, and primary producers' organisations. By M24, 88 key actors had been approached, 19 participated in project actions, and 16 collaborated in supporting BioRural implementation.

The engagement actions saw significant increases from M12 to M24: communications (58 to 88 key actors), meetings (11 to 21), participation (4 to 19), and collaborations (10 to 16). The key actors' activation map in Figure 5 illustrates the effectiveness of period M12-M24 in expanding project awareness and engagement driven by project actions (workshops on knowledge exchange and capacity building of WP3).

Regarding ERBN subscription, the initial target of 20 organisations by M24 was surpassed, reaching 31 users. This was facilitated by tailored contacts following the project's national strategy and project actions. Research and education entities and company organisations showed the highest subscription eagerness. Future efforts should focus on making the network more dynamic to attract individual stakeholders, who currently see less value in subscribing.

2.3 SE RBP Results – Status at M24

2.3.1 SE RBP Overview

The BioRural South-East Rural Bioeconomy Platform (SE RBP) is built by 4 countries: Greece, Slovenia, Romania and North Macedonia. Among them, Greece behaves internally as head of the RBP, adopting the role of RBP leader. Each country developed a specific strategy for key actors’ engagement at M12, which can be consulted as an Annex to D2.1.

In the present summary the aggregated figures of SE RBP are presented, with specific insights to individual country highlights at the end of this subsection.

SE RBP: Key actors profile in the strategy

BioRural partners performed by M12 individual analysis by country, to identify which key actors would be relevant for supporting BioRural actions in their own country, and to engage to participate, collaborate and become part of the community of the European Rural Bioeconomy Network.

The analysis led to each BioRural country to elaborate by M12 a list of key actors, including the organisation profile, key bioeconomy topics and relevance for the project. As the project advanced after M12, partners have detected additional key actors who had not been considered at the initial moment. The status of identified key actors at M24 is presented next in Figure 7 arranged by profiles. Additionally, Table 5 indicates the KPIs planned in general for the whole project, showing key actors profiles and the bioeconomy topics of interest.

Figure 7. SE RBP: summary of identified key actors profiles by M24

In respect M12, at M24 a total of new additional 49 key actors have been added to the identified key actors considered as potentially relevant to support BioRural actions and widen project impacts. As observed in Figure 7, at M24 the total key actors identified add **329 organisations in the 4 RBP countries**. It is predominant the profile of companies, as potential facilitators of biobased solutions. As well Research and Education organizations, primary producers, government and projects are considered key actors in the purpose of BIORURAL implementation and ERBN establishment.

In respect the bioeconomy topics covered by these key actors, they are presented in Table 5. As we saw in the first report (M12) the bioeconomy topics covered by these key actors already identified, they are presented in Table 9. As observed the prevailing class Theme is “Agriculture” as well as “Horizontal”, the latter especially because research centers and universities initially addressed cover most of the bioeconomy themes. These actors including of Rural organizations, consultants, Networks, etc. are more prone to find value in the multiple project products, since they are not “theme specific”. On the other side, it is evident that the topic on forest and also the aquatic bioeconomy areas are less represented than the others. This is logical as predominant resource areas of bioeconomy in Slovenia, Romania and North Macedonia are agriculture and forestry, given their predominant inland areas and economy. Notwithstanding these topics are as well to be addressed in all countries, therefore requiring further exploring and advance after M12.

Table 5. SE RBP: Bioeconomy themes and strategy KPIs as planned at M24 of project

Period: M1-M36 Bioeconomy theme	TOTAL		Nr. By profile								
	Nr	%	#PP or #PPOrg	#Comp or #Comp.Org	#Cons or #Cons.Org	#RU or #RU.Org	#Gov	#R/Ed	#Net	#Proj	#Oth
[Agr/F] Agri/F	109	28%	23	30	3	7	5	22	3	14	2
[For] Forest	32	8%	4	6	2	3	3	9	0	3	2
[Aq] Aquatic	47	12%	11	11	1	1	4	15	0	2	2
[BE] Bioenergy	42	11%	0	26	1	1	1	5	2	6	0
[BM] Biomaterials	51	13%	0	32	0	0	0	12	1	4	2
[Hor] Horizontal	98	25%	1	12	10	10	21	12	5	15	12
[Nspec] Non specific	8	2%	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	5
TOTAL (Nr)	387	100%	39	118	17	22	34	76	11	45	25
TOTAL (%)	100%	100%	10%	30%	4%	6%	9%	20%	3%	12%	6%

IMPORTANT NOTE: this table summarises the tags, to identify if all bioeconomy themes are being covered in the strategy to approach key actors. Since several key actors have been tagged with more than one tag, the total accounting of tags (387) is larger than the total number of key actors (329).

RBP SE: Status at M24 (August 2024)

Activation of the key actors started by carrying out communications and meetings. During this first stage, **by end of August 2023** (Month 12 of project) the **SE RBP partners considered more relevant initially 146 out of the 280 key actors identified**. After this initial stage, it is considered the rest of actors may be object of approach as the diverse BioRural key actions or key stages take place. Therefore, the whole set of actors identified (329) are in principle potentially targeted in the period M12-M24.

As observed in Table 6, total of **238 actors have been objects of communication** leading to a total of 254 meetings. These communications have triggered **the effect of 103 key actors having already either participated** (as audience by attending events, meetings, workshops) **or collaborated** (by supporting project, as by providing data, vision, connecting with other actors, or co-organising workshops or events), **or both of them, adding 136 participations and 105 collaborations**.

Of the **238 key actors identified, 91 remain at the moment inactive** and not aware of the project (at least there is no evidence of their awareness and interest).

Table 6. SE RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M24

ACTIONS	Nr. KEY ACTORS		TOTAL NR of actions		Interpretation (figures at M24)
	M12	M24	M12	M24	
Communications	132	238	132	238	Communications are informative or “ice-breaking” contacts performed to make aware of BioRural exists, and its aims. But they are not engagement actions. <i>A total of 238 key actors have been object of communication with either emails or calls.</i>
Meetings	95	191	109	254	<u>Meetings are direct actions of engagement</u> (visits, in person talk, phone or e-meetings) where partners explain value and try to activate interest, so that key actors will take part into BioRural actions. <i>A total of 191 key actors approached, few of them with more than one meeting, totaling 254 meetings.</i>
Participations	55	103	58	136	<u>Participation refers to</u> take part in a project action, meaning key actors is active, but not meaning they are supporting project actions. Examples are: participate as audience in a seminar or workshop, respond a survey, etc. <i>A total of 103 key actors have participated in BioRural actions by M24. Several of them participated in more than one actions (adding a total of 136 participations). Among these 103 key actors, 56 of them have also collaborated, meaning that 47 can be considered active, but not still engaged (see Figure 4).</i>
Collaborations	24	81	25	105	<u>Collaboration means</u> that engagement has been successful to trigger key actors to support BioRural actions: by collaborating in organising a workshop, by engaging other stakeholders to participate in project surveys, etc. <i>A total of 81 key actors have collaborated with BioRural. Several of them collaborated not just once, and therefore 105 collaborations took place.</i>

As observed in Table 6 a total of 238 actors have been object of communication leading to a total of 254 meetings. These communications have triggered the effect of 103 key actors having already participated in project actions (surveys, workshops mainly at this project stage) and 81 of them already collaborated (by supporting in providing data, vision, widening project dissemination or reaching new target actors, for example in the surveying work. From the 329 key actors identified, 91 remain at the moment inactive and not aware of the project (at least there is no evidence of their awareness and interest). These figures are also displayed visually and disaggregated in Figure 8 by key actor profile.

Figure 8. SE RBP: status of activation of key actors at M24. LEFT: Targeted VS Achieved contacts. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor

As observed in Figure 8 (left) during the period M12-M24 the SE RBP partners faced to potentially contact and or engage the whole set of identified key actors (totaling 329). Partners have finally approached (aware, active or engaged) 238 of them by M24. The remaining 91 actors identified (in each country) will be object to consideration during period M24-M36, to optimise project results. This may lead to realise several key actors initially thought to be targeted, to not be relevant anymore, and thus to steer the strategy accordingly in collaborations with key actors already engaged and resulting strategical for the successful implementation of BioRural actions.

As relevant project actions took place several participations and collaborations were being triggered. Among the 238 key actors object of contact for awareness, a total of 128 have already participated and/or collaborated, meaning:

- 47 key actors have participated, but not collaborated; thus they reach the status of “active”
- 81 actors have collaborated, meaning they reached the status of “engaged” with BioRural. It must be noted that several of these actors, 56 in total, have done both, participate and collaborate. Notwithstanding in terms of degree of engagement they are classified with the superior stage, “engaged”.

RBP SE key actors analysis and next steps

To further identify the status of advance in the engagement of key actors, each country partner has performed an analysis to cross-check the degree of activation with the relevance that the key actors may have for project implementation and growth of ERBN in their countries. It has been analysed using the “quadrant diagram” (methodology and explanation provided in D2.1, section 2.2.2).

Figure 9 shows by RBP country the evolution of the key actors from M12 (August 2023) until M24 (August 2024).

KEY ACTORS ENGAGEMENT STATUS AND EVOLUTION by M24

Status at M12

Actions of engagement and incorporation to BioRural actions

Status reached at M24

Figure 9. SE RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M24

In respect the planning for the next period (M24 – M36), it has been agreed inside the project to continue the logical actions as next:

- 1) Concentrate in more relevant key actors to make them move towards the right-side of the graph, meaning their status of activation in respect BioRural and the ERBN improves.

Relevant and crucial key actors to be contacted to pass (at least) from...			
...inactive...		... to aware	Communication actions and meetings. Showing the value of BioRural ACTIONS
...aware...		... to active	...showing the specific actions where they can get value
...active...		... to engaged	...offering to collaborate in actions of their high interest

- 2) As project evolves continue discovering new key actors that may be interested to be object of communication, to incorporate to the tracking

Specific details and highlights by each SE RBP country is presented below.

RBP SE: ERBN and adhesion of key actors and another stakeholders

In the initial planning set by SE RBP partners, it was set a target of achieving 80 key actors to be part of the ERBN community by end of August 2024 (BioRural project Month 24). The individual minimum target was set by country to reach at least 20 organisations enrolled by the mentioned date. This enrolment can take place and can be proved by:

- persons registering into the toolkit (key actors or stakeholders organisations)
- alternatively, under reception of a formal statement (email or letter) of their intend to collaborate with BioRural and the ERBN (mostly key actors).

At month M24 the achievements are summarised into Figure 10. As observed on the left side at M24 a total of 149 persons from key actors or stakeholders are considered as ERBN members. A total of 136 have subscribed to the ERBN by registering through the BioRural toolkit, whereas 13 have done it by formally agreeing to support BioRural and ERBN. This total of 149 members of the ERBN complies with the minimum target set of 80 to be reached by M24. This shows an outstanding contribution from the SE RBP in the path to start growing the ERBN community.

Among these 149 members, 103 persons belong to key actors organisations and 46 to stakeholders organisations. Stakeholders have not been object of direct communication, but have subscribed either after been aware of BioRural through communication (social media, posts, news, fairs, etc.) or after participating in any of BioRural actions (workshops, tutorials, events, etc.). This aggregation of key actors and stakeholders in connection through a platform, interested in innovation, bioeconomy and application of new small scale solutions, is a principal value which in return is expected to attract more organisations to enrol into the ERBN in the next period (by M36, August 2025).

As observed Figure 10 (right) depicts the distribution of the 136 persons from SE RBP registered in the ERBN through the BioRural toolkit. As we can see in the graph, there is a distribution of different stakeholders and key actors among of the four SE RBP countries. The majority of them are research and education institutions or even Universities with a number of 49 registrations. Also, very important part in this graph has the private companies and self-employed registrations with 48 stakeholders. Associations and clusters together with NGOs are distributing in a very good level with 27 registrations and we can see with around 6 registrations coming from government and public administration.

Figure 10. SE RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M24. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile

2.3.2 Highlights by SE RBP country: Greece, Slovenia, Romania and North Macedonia

The general planning of the strategies for Greece, Slovenia, Romania and North Macedonia is available as an Annex to D2.1. Here a brief update and main highlights of the M24 status are presented.

GREECE

At the end of M12 a good engagement had been reached principally with Research and Education organisations with around 13 subscriptions. Afterwards the evolution has expanded to other key actors necessary to organise the T3.2 workshops. As such several primary producers' organisations were contacted and involved. The reaction was positive, and we achieved the number of 13 private companies and organizations subscribed to the toolkit. The interaction with the National CAP network proceeded most operatively through regional delegates (called "antennas") in charge of regional dissemination and monitoring local AKIS networks. It was achieved during the Greek workshops. At National level last project stage may be appropriate to establish contact at higher level. Additionally, the number of the key actors and the future subscribed numbers are expected to be higher duo to the series of workshops and exploitation events that Biorural Project is participating in. As observed, from the 60 key actors initially targeted a total of 45 have been activated: 15 remain inactive after the communications and meetings, though are expected to participate in future actions, as project expands. In respect ERBN subscription the target by M24 was initially set to 20 organisations. This figure was already surpassed at M12, with a total of 40 members adhered to ERBN community. At the current status a total community of 40 users can be considered as part of ERBN. Among them 34 have already subscribed through the toolkit, even though additional 6 organisations have declared interest into ERBN, though not eager to subscribe through the platform.

SLOVENIA

At M24, the total number of key actors identified in Slovenia amounts to 125. In the last period M12-24, another 17 key actors were added to the table. These actors were involved in cooperation in various tasks related to relevant bioeconomy and rural development projects, in particular in the implementation of the national workshops (T3.2) and the documentation of new success cases (T2.2). By M24, a total of 80 key actors had been approached, of which 23 had already participated in at least one project measure and 18 had already collaborated to support the implementation of BioRural (e.g. as co-organisers of the T3.2 workshops or by building bridges to other organisations).

The good development of the involvement of the main actors in the project measures can be clearly seen in Figure 9 with the quadrant diagrams. It is clear that the quadrants on the far right (i.e. the actors who are already engaged and collaborating) are more densely populated than the diagrams at M12. Notwithstanding the period from M24

to M36, consideration needs to be given to making efforts to involve key organisations in either project activities or ERBN maintenance.

In terms of ERBN subscriptions, the target for M24 was originally set at 20 organisations. This target has been exceeded as a total of 38 organisations have joined the network to date. Some stakeholders that were not the focus of this strategy have joined ERBN as a result of several on-site activities (workshops, networking events and dissemination events).

ROMANIA

At M24 the total key actors identified adds a total of 89. A total of 25 key actors have been added in the period M12-M24, as they were necessary collaborators for the regional workshops under T3.2 or other dissemination events. The newly added stakeholders represent mainly EU-funded bioeconomy projects, research and educational institutions, NGOs in the field, consulting companies as well as media organisations. A total of 69 actors have been approached, leading to 52 having already participated in at least one project action, and 25 of them having already collaborated, supporting BioRural implementation.

A positive evolution of the involvement of key actors into project actions can be observed with the quadrant graphs. It is evident that key actors are engaged and collaborating with BioRural project and the graph is more densely populated at M24 than it was in the previous reporting.

In respect ERBN subscription, target by M24 was initially set to 20 organisations. At the current status, and as presented below in Figure 18, a total number of 43 users can be considered as part of ERBN. Among them 35 have already subscribed through the toolkit, and an additional 8 organisations have declared interest into ERBN, though not necessarily intend to subscribe to the online platform.

NORTH MACEDONIA

The total number of key actors identified at M24 is 55. In the period M12-M24, additional 3 key actors have been added, as they were identified during the organisation of the national workshops (T3.2). A total of 44 key actors have been approached until M24, from which 14 have already participated in at least one project action, and 7 of them have already collaborated, supporting the project implementation (e.g. as co-organiser of national workshops T3.2, participating as speakers in online knowledge exchange workshops T3.1, participating as success stories T2.4, or by providing contacts of other relevant stakeholders).

Concerning the engagement status, it is worth highlighting that by M24, key actors generally have increased participation and collaboration in project activities compared to M12 and the main key actors' profiles engaged are research and education organisations, government institutions, companies or their organisations as well as primary producers' organisations. However, in the last period from M24 to M36 it is expected that final effort will be invested in greater involvement of key organisations in project activities and ERBN maintenance.

In respect of ERBN subscription, the target that was initially set to 20 organisations by M24 has been achieved. By M12, 12 organisations have been registered to the ERBN, and this number has increased to a total of 24 subscriptions by M24. The subscription process to ERBN has been progressing very well, according to the initial planning and expectations. It can be considered that the subscription from research and education institutions and government institutions as key actors is more straightforward and easier than with other key actors.

2.4 NW RBP Results – Status at M24

2.4.1 RBP NW Overview

The BioRural North-West Rural Bioeconomy Platform (NW RBP) is built by 4 countries: The Netherlands, Denmark, Germany and France. Among them, The Netherlands behaves internally as head of the RBP, adopting the role of RBP leader. Each country developed a specific strategy for key actors engagement at M12, which can be consulted as an Annex to D2.1.

In the present summary the aggregated figures of NW RBP are presented, with specific insights to individual country highlights at the end of this sub-section.

NW RBP: Key actors profile in the strategy

BioRural partners performed by M12 individual analysis by country, to identify which key actors would be relevant for supporting BioRural actions in their own country, and to engage to participate, collaborate and become part of the community of the European Rural Bioeconomy Network.

The analysis led to each BioRural country to elaborate by M12 a list of key actors, including the organisation profile, key bioeconomy topics and relevance for the project. As the project advanced after M12, partners have detected additional key actors who had not been considered at the initial moment. The status of identified key actors at M24 is presented next in Figure 11 arranged by profiles. Additionally Table 7 indicates the KPIs planned in general for the whole project, showing key actors profiles and the bioeconomy topics of interest.

Figure 11. NW RBP: summary of identified key actors profiles by M24

In respect M12, at M24 a total of new additional **72** key actors have been added to the identified key actors considered as potentially relevant to support BioRural actions and widen project impacts. As observed in Figure 11, at M24 the total key actors identified add **318 organisations in the 4 RBP countries**.

The structure of the NW RBP key actor profile is similar to that of M12. Where the predominant profiles are mainly those of companies and company organisation. However, we do see an increase in the number of key actors in the profiles of Consultants and consultant organisation, plus Research and Education. This is a likely positive side effect of the national workshops held last year for T3.2, for which there was great collaboration with Universities and higher schools, and in which individual consultants were mostly interested.

As observed the prevailing class Theme is “Companies”, as in M12, especially because the direct networks in NW consists of companies and company organisations and those who are initially addressed cover most of the bioeconomy themes. The actors including of Rural organisations, consultants, Networks, etc. are more prone to find value in the multiple project products, since they are not “theme specific”. As such, being part of the AKIS system in each country, they can be very strategic to convey the innovation stories and ideas towards the potential

adopters. Remarkably, unlike M12, the topics related to aquatic grew strongly in terms of representativeness. This is due to the national workshops in T3.2. on this topic. This clearly broadened the network of partners.

Table 7. NW RBP: Bioeconomy themes and strategy KPIs as planned at M24 of project

Period: M1-M36 Bioeconomy theme	TOTAL		Nr. By profile								
	Nr	%	#PP or #PPOrg	#Comp or #Comp.Org	#Cons or #Cons.Org	#RU or #RU.Org	#Gov	#R/Ed	#Net	#Proj	#Oth
[Agr/F] Agri/F	66	21%	17	19	1	2	4	8	15	0	0
[For] Forest	22	7%	3	5	2	2	0	1	9	0	0
[Aq] Aquatic	36	11%	1	16	2	0	0	12	1	2	2
[BE] Bioenergy	25	8%	1	13	6	1	1	1	1	1	0
[BM] Biomaterials	67	21%	1	43	8	1	0	5	8	1	0
[Hor] Horizontal	56	18%	1	4	2	8	15	13	6	7	0
[Nspec] Non specific	47	15%	1	5	6	3	3	16	9	1	3
TOTAL (Nr)	319	100%	25	105	27	17	23	56	49	12	5
TOTAL (%)	100%	100%	8%	33%	8%	5%	7%	18%	15%	4%	2%

IMPORTANT NOTE: this table summarises the tags, to identify if all bioeconomy themes are being covered in the strategy to approach key actors. Since one of the key actors has been tagged with more than one tag, the total accounting of tags (319) is larger than the total number of key actors (318).

RBP NW: Status at M24 (August 2024)

Activation of the key actors started by carrying out communications and meetings. During this first stage, **by end of August 2023** (Month 12 of project) the **NW RBP partners considered more relevant initially 130 out of the 246 key actors identified**. After this initial stage, it is considered the rest of actors may be object of approach as the diverse BioRural key actions or key stages take place. Therefore, the whole set of actors identified (318) are in principle potentially targeted in the period M12-M24.

As observed in Table 8, a total of **161 actors have been object of communication** leading to a total of **181 meetings**. These communications have triggered **the effect of 139 key actors having already either participated** (as audience by attending events, meetings, workshops) **or collaborated** (by supporting project, as by providing data, vision, connecting with other actors, or co-organising workshops or events), **or both of them, adding 123 participations and 33 collaborations**.

From the **318 key actors identified**, **131 remain at the moment inactive** and not aware of the project (at least there is no evidence of their awareness and interest).

Table 8. NW RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M24

ACTIONS	Nr. KEY ACTORS		TOTAL NR of actions		Interpretation (figures at M24)
	M12	M24	M12	M24	
Communications	88	161	88	161	Communications are informative or "ice-breaking" contacts performed to make aware of BioRural exists, and its aims. But they are not engagement actions. <i>A total of 161 key actors have been object of communication with either emails or calls.</i>
Meetings	69	160	76	181	<u>Meetings are direct actions of engagement</u> (visits, in person talk, phone or e-meetings) where partners explain value and try to activate interest, so that key actors will take part into BioRural actions. <i>A total of 160 key actors approached, few of them with more than one meeting, totalling 181 meetings.</i>
Participations	54	110	65	123	<u>Participation refers to</u> take part in a project action, meaning key actors is active, but not meaning they are supporting project actions. Examples are: participate as audience in a seminar or workshop, respond a survey, etc. <i>A total of 110 key actors have participated in BioRural actions by M24. Several of them participated in more than one action (adding a total of 123 participations).</i>

					Among these 110 key actors, 29 of them have also collaborated, meaning that 131 can be considered active, but not still engaged (see Figure 4).
Collaborations	5	29	5	33	Collaboration means that engagement has been successful to trigger key actors to support BioRural actions: by collaborating in organising a workshop, by engaging other stakeholders to participate in project surveys, etc. A total of 29 key actors have collaborated with BioRural. Several of them collaborated not just once, and therefore 33 collaborations took place.

As observed in the period M12 to M24 the increase of 72 actors, who have been object of communication, leading to a increase of 91 meetings. These communications have triggered the effect of 110 key actors having already participated in project actions. And 29 of them have already collaborated. (by supporting in providing data, vision, broadening project dissemination or reaching new target actors, for example in the surveying work). Through the workshops in T3.2, among others, several new meetings have occurred, with a particular focus on new participations and collaborations taking place. The latter indicates that within our RBP we were able to make key actors active through participation and engaged through collaboration with the project. This serves as a clear indicator that the project does not evolve in isolation but in connection with key actors who can amplify the project's effects.

These figures are also displayed visually and disaggregated in Figure 12 by key actor profile.

Figure 12. NW RBP: status of activation of key actors at M24. LEFT: Targeted VS Achieved contacts. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor

As observed in Figure 12 (left) during the period M12-M24 the SW RBP partners faced to potentially contact and or engage the whole set of identified key actors (totaling 318). Partners have finally approached (aware, active or engaged) 187 of them by M24. The remaining 131 actors identified (in each country) will be object to consideration during period M24-M36, to optimise project results. This may lead to realise several key actors initially thought to be targeted, to not be relevant anymore, and thus to steer the strategy accordingly in collaborations with key actors already engaged and resulting strategical for the successful implementation of BioRural actions.

As relevant project actions took place several participations and collaborations were being triggered. Among the 187 key actors object of contact for awareness, a total of 117 have already participated and/or collaborated, meaning:

- 88 key actors have participated, but not collaborated; thus they reach the status of “active”
- 29 key actors have collaborated, meaning they reached the status of “engaged” with BioRural. It must be noted that several of these actors, 22 in total, have done both, participate and collaborate. Notwithstanding in terms of degree of engagement they are classified with the superior stage, “engaged”.

RBP NW key actors analysis and next steps

To further identify the status of advance in the engagement of key actors, each country partner has performed an analysis to cross-check the degree of activation with the relevance that the key actors may have for project implementation and growth of ERBN in their countries. It has been analysed using the “quadrant diagram” (methodology and explanation provided in D2.1, section 2.2.2).

Figure 13 shows by RBP country the evolution of the key actors from M12 (August 2023) until M24 (August 2024).

Figure 13. NW RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M24

In respect the planning for the next period (M24 – M36), it has been agreed inside the project to continue the logical actions as next:

- 1) Concentrate in more relevant key actors to make them move towards the right-side of the graph, meaning their status of activation in respect BioRural and the ERBN improves.

Relevant and crucial key actors to be contacted to pass (at least) from...			
...inactive...		... to aware	Communication actions and meetings. Showing the value of BioRural ACTIONS
...aware...		... to active	...showing the specific actions where they can get value
...active...		... to engaged	...offering to collaborate in actions of their high interest

- 2) As project evolves continue discovering new key actors that may be interested to be object of communication, to incorporate to the tracking

Specific details and highlights by each NW RBP country is presented below.

RBP NW: ERBN and adhesion of key actors and another stakeholders

In the initial planning set by NW RBP partners, it was set a target of achieving 80 members to be part of the ERBN community by end of August 2024 (BioRural project Month 24). The individual minimum target was set by country to reach at least 20 organisations enrolled by the mentioned date. This enrolment can take place and can be proved by:

- persons registering into the toolkit (key actors or stakeholders organisations)
- alternatively, under reception of a formal statement (email or letter) of their intend to collaborate with BioRural and the ERBN (mostly key actors).

At month M24 the achievements are summarised into Figure 14. As observed on the left side at M24 a total of 95 persons have subscribed to the ERBN, corresponding to either key actors or stakeholders organisations. A total of 76 have subscribed to the ERBN by registering through the BioRural toolkit, whereas 19 have done it by formally agreeing to support BioRural and ERBN registered through the BioRural toolkit. This total of 95 members of the ERBN complies with the minimum target set of 80 to be reached by M24. This shows a good contribution from the NW RBP in the path to start growing the ERBN community..

Among these 95 organisations, 72 belong to key actors organisations and 23 to stakeholders organisations. Stakeholders have not been object of direct communication, but have subscribed either after been aware of BioRural through communication (social media, posts, news, fairs, etc.) or after participating in any of BioRural actions (workshops, tutorials, events, etc.). This aggregation of key actors and stakeholders in connection through a platform, interested in innovation, bioeconomy and application of new small scale solutions, is a principal value which in return is expected to attract more organisations to enrol into the ERBN in the next period (by M36, August 2025).

As observed Figure 14 (right) depicts the distribution of the 95 members from NW RBP registered in the ERBN through the BioRural toolkit of by formal declaration at M24. The principal group correspond to individual companies, which is coherent as the efforts placed by NW partners in the engagement during these 24 months have been targeted to private companies. In this line, the clusters and associations, mainly from private sector, add also a good share of the ERBN members from NW RBP. Research and education and government are less relevant in number, as result of the strategies in NW countries, and also resembling a lower proneness of public administrations to register in these type of platforms.

Figure 14. NW RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN. By M24 LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile

2.4.2 Highlights by NW RBP country: The Netherlands, Denmark, Germany and France

The general planning of the strategies for The Netherlands, Denmark, Germany and France is available as an Annex to D2.1. Here a brief update and main highlights of the M24 status are presented.

The general planning of the strategies for The Netherlands, Denmark, Germany and France is available as an Annex to D2.1. Here a brief update and main highlights of the M24 status are presented.

The NETHERLANDS

In the period M12-M24, a total of 21 new key actors have been added, thus The Netherlands now have identified a total of 66 key actors. Two new success cases on bioenergy and food and agriculture have been reported under T2.4. Collaboration in organization of and conduction of the Dutch regional workshops under T3.2 was a good opportunity for launching the BioRural project. The workshops did lead to engagement of several new stakeholders, especially on the aquatic biomass. Which led to several collaborations and supported BioRural implementation.

In the Netherlands, the principal profiles active and collaborating are dominated by companies or their organizations, as well as primary producers' organisations. New in this period are research and education organizations. The numbers have improved (in respect M12) for all profiles.

The evolution of the involvement of key actors into project actions is well observed into the quadrant graphs. In this, it is evidenced that many stakeholders are aware of the platform and project, and a good tendency is achieved as the rightmost quadrants are more populated than at M12.

ERBN membership target by M24 was set to 20. This figure has been not been fully reached by official toolkit subscriptions (only 7) but counting with the declared interest of additional 14 persons from key actors and stakeholders organisations.

Contact and involvement of public authorities and local advisory institutions and individuals is important for the development of local biobased solutions. Here, the involvement of more new actors could be desired, and this will be the focus for the Netherlands.

DENMARK

In the period M12-M24, a total of 37 new key actors have been added, thus Denmark now have identified a total of 88 key actors. Two success cases have been reported under T2.4. Collaboration in organization of and conduction of the Danish regional workshops under T3.2 was a good opportunity for launching the BioRural project. The

workshops did lead to engagement of several stakeholders. Current status is that 9 key actors have collaborated and supported BioRural implementation.

In Denmark, the principal profiles active and collaborating are dominated by companies or their organizations, but also research and education organizations as well as primary producers' organizations and government institutions are represented. The numbers have improved (in respect M12) for all profiles especially for research and education organizations and companies.

The evolution of the involvement of key actors into project actions is well observed into the quadrant graphs. It is there evident how the rightmost quadrants (meaning actors already engaged and collaborating) is more densely populated than the graph at M12.

ERBN subscription target by M24 was set to 20. This figure has been reached. All 20 have already subscribed through the toolkit, and other key actors have declared interest into ERBN and will subscribe the platform.

Contact and involvement of public authorities and local advisory institutions and individuals is important for the development of local biobased solutions. Here, the involvement of more new actors could be desired, and this will be the focus for Denmark.

GERMANY

At M24 the total key actors identified for Germany are 93. Additionally, a total of 2 key actors have been added in the period M12-M24, as they were new collaborators for the regional workshops under T3.2 and in terms of several events as communication activity for WP5. The distribution is as next: mostly represented are networks, than companies and their organisations as well as research and education. At M24 a total of 29 key actors have been approached, leading to 18 having already participated in at least one project action, and 11 of them having already collaborated, supporting BioRural implementation (e.g. as co-organiser of T3.2 workshops, or by bridging towards other organisations).

The good evolution of the involvement of key actors into project actions is proceeding well, as presented in the quadrant graphs, since the rightmost quadrants (meaning actors already engaged and collaborating) is more densely populated than the graph at M12. At period M24 to M36 it must be reconsidered to invest efforts to involve key organisations either in project actions or into ERBN maintenance.

In respect ERBN subscription target by M24 was initially set to 20 organisations. At the current status, a total community of 21 users can be considered as part of ERBN. Among them 19 have already subscribed through the toolkit, additional 2 organisations have declared interest into ERBN, though not eager to subscribe through the platform.

FRANCE

The period from M12 to M24 (August 2023 to August 2024) was marked by intensive communication actions carried out by Valorial. These actions included the distribution of the monthly newsletter "La Live", publications on LinkedIn via the Valorial account, as well as workshops organised as part of T3.3. In addition, contacts were made at other internal events.

Positive elements observed :

- Regional commitment: Interactions with regional institutions and departments of agriculture have borne fruit, particularly with the Pays de la Loire region, which is actively involved in disseminating BioRural events and promoting the platform.
- Support from organisations: Several business support organisations continue to show a strong interest in BioRural. These organisations took part in several T3.3 workshops and are keen to encourage collaboration between BioRural and projects with potential synergies.

Structural difficulties identified :

- Perception of added value: Since it is freely accessible, potential key players do not always see the point of registering on the platform.
- Technical problems: Registration on the platform is hampered when e-mail addresses contain special characters, which discourages companies after a single attempt.

Outlook for M24 to M36:

We anticipate an increase in registrations thanks to reinforced communication, with actions on the ground such as networking and dissemination events, as well as increased communication on the platform during internal events.

2.5 NE RBP Results – Status at M24

2.5.1 RBP NE Overview

The BioRural North-East Rural Bioeconomy Platform (NE RBP) is built by 3 countries: Poland, Latvia and Lithuania. Among them, Poland behaves internally as head of the RBP, adopting the role of RBP leader. Each country developed a specific strategy for key actors engagement at M12, which can be consulted as an Annex to D2.1.

In the present summary the aggregated figures of NE RBP are presented, with specific insights to individual country highlights at the end of this sub-section.

NE RBP: Key actors profile in the strategy

BioRural partners performed by M12 individual analysis by country, to identify which key actors would be relevant for supporting BioRural actions in their own country, and to engage to participate, collaborate and become part of the community of the European Rural Bioeconomy Network.

The analysis led to each BioRural country to elaborate by M12 a list of key actors, including the organisation profile, key bioeconomy topics and relevance for the project. As the project advanced after M12, partners have detected additional key actors who had not been considered at the initial moment. The status of identified key actors at M24 is presented next in Figure 15 arranged by profiles. Additionally, Table 9 indicates the KPIs planned in general for the whole project, showing key actors profiles and the bioeconomy topics of interest.

Figure 15. NE RBP: summary of identified key actors profiles by M24

In respect M12, at M24 a total of new additional 56 key actors have been added to the identified key actors considered as potentially relevant to support BioRural actions and widen project impacts. As observed in Figure

15, at M24 the total key actors identified add **101 organisations in the 3 RBP countries**. The predominant profiles in 2024 in compare to M12 were not changed, they have only increased in numbers.

In respect the bioeconomy topics covered by these key actors, they are presented in Table 9. As observed the prevailing class Theme is Agriculture and Aquatic. The high growth in aquatic system in compare to M12 was caused by a broader advertising campaign aimed at getting this group of stakeholders interested in the project.

Table 9. NE RBP: Bioeconomy themes and strategy KPIs as planned at M24 of project

Period: M1-M36 Bioeconomy theme	TOTAL		Nr. By profile								
	Nr	%	#PP or #PPOrg	#Comp or #Comp.Org	#Cons or #Cons.Org	#RU or #RU.Org	#Gov	#R/Ed	#Net	#Proj	#Oth
[Agr/F] Agri/F	69	24%	18	8	2	11	8	12	5	4	1
[For] Forest	19	7%	1	4	1	3	2	4	3	1	0
[Aq] Aquatic	60	21%	30	4	11	1	2	7	1	0	4
[BE] Bioenergy	44	15%	2	11	2	8	6	8	6	0	1
[BM] Biomaterials	36	13%	1	20	0	4	2	6	2	1	0
[Hor] Horizontal	42	15%	0	3	3	9	8	9	5	2	3
[Nspec] Non specific	15	5%	0	3	7	1	3	0	0	0	1
TOTAL (Nr)	285	100%	52	53	26	37	31	46	22	8	10
TOTAL (%)	100%	100%	18%	19%	9%	13%	11%	16%	8%	3%	4%

IMPORTANT NOTE: this table summarises the tags, to identify if all bioeconomy themes are being covered in the strategy to approach key actors. Since several key actors have been tagged with more than one tag, the total accounting of tags (285) is larger than the total number of key actors (243).

RBP NE: Status at M24 (August 2024)

Activation of the key actors started by carrying out communications and meetings. During this first stage, **by end of August 2023** (Month 12 of project) the **NE RBP partners considered more relevant initially 86 out of the 153 key actors identified**. After this initial stage, it is considered the rest of actors may be object of approach as the diverse BioRural key actions or key stages take place. Therefore the whole set of actors identified (251) are in principle potentially targeted in the period M12-M24.

As observed in Table 10, a total of **243 actors have been object of communication** leading to a total of 196 meetings. These communications have triggered **the effect of 113 key actors having already either participated** (as audience by attending events, meetings, workshops) **or collaborated** (by supporting project, as by providing data, vision, connecting with other actors, or co-organising workshops or events), **or both of them, adding 51 participations and 77 collaborations**.

From the 251 key actors identified, 8 remain at the moment inactive and not aware of the project (at least there is no evidence of their awareness and interest).

Table 10. NE RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M24

ACTIONS	Nr. KEY ACTORS		TOTAL NR of actions		Interpretation (figures at M24)
	M12	M24	M12	M24	
Communications	82	243	82	243	Communications are informative or "ice-breaking" contacts performed to make aware of BioRural exists, and its aims. But they are not engagement actions. <i>A total of 243 key actors have been object of communication with either emails or calls.</i>

Meetings	44	113	49	196	<p><u>Meetings are direct actions of engagement</u> (visits, in person talk, phone or e-meetings) where partners explain value and try to activate interest, so that key actors will take part into BioRural actions.</p> <p><i>A total of 113 key actors approached, few of them with more than one meeting, totaling 196 meetings.</i></p>
Participations	45	97	45	151	<p><u>Participation refers to</u> take part in a project action, meaning key actors is active, but not meaning they are supporting project actions. Examples are: participate as audience in a seminar or workshop, respond a survey, etc.</p> <p><i>A total of 97 key actors have participated in BioRural actions by M24. Several of them participated in more than one action (adding a total of 151 participations). Among these 97 key actors, 62 of them have also collaborated, meaning that 35 can be considered active, but not still engaged (see Figure 4).</i></p>
Collaborations	27	65	27	77	<p><u>Collaboration means</u> that engagement has been successful to trigger key actors to support BioRural actions: by collaborating in organising a workshop, by engaging other stakeholders to participate in project surveys, etc.</p> <p><i>A total of 65 key actors have collaborated with BioRural. Several of them collaborated not just once, and therefore 77 collaborations took place.</i></p>

As observed in the period M12 to M24 the increase of meetings, participations and collaborations was significant, this is related to the development of the project as well as the large number of workshops organized by the project. Cooperation with partners is going well. Key actors support and promote activities and support the acquisition of new members, but above all they support the spread of knowledge.

These figures are also displayed visually and disaggregated in Figure 16 by key actor profile.

Figure 16. NE RBP: status of activation of key actors at M24. LEFT: Targeted VS Achieved contacts. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor

As observed in Figure 16 (left) during the period M12-M24 the SW RBP partners faced to potentially contact and or engage the whole set of identified key actors (totaling 251). Partners have finally approached (aware, active or engaged) 243 of them by M24. The remaining 8 actors identified (in each country) will be object to consideration during period M24-M36, to optimise project results. This may lead to realise several key actors initially thought to be targeted, to not be relevant anymore, and thus to steer the strategy accordingly in collaborations with key actors already engaged and resulting strategical for the successful implementation of BioRural actions.

As relevant project actions took place several participations and collaborations were being triggered. Among the 243 key actors object of contact for awareness, a total of 100 have already participated and/or collaborated, meaning:

- 97 key actors have participated, but not collaborated; thus they reach the status of “active”
- 65 actors have collaborated, meaning they reached the status of “engaged” with BioRural. It must be noted that several of these actors, 62 in total, have done both, participate and collaborate. Notwithstanding in terms of degree of engagement they are classified with the superior stage, “engaged”.

RBP NE key actors analysis and next steps

To further identify the status of advance in the engagement of key actors, each country partner has performed an analysis to cross-check the degree of activation with the relevance that the key actors may have for project implementation and growth of ERBN in their countries. It has been analysed using the “quadrant diagram” (methodology and explanation provided in D2.1, section 2.2.2).

Figure 17 shows by RBP country the evolution of the key actors from M12 (August 2023) until M24 (August 2024).

Figure 17. NE RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M24

In respect the planning for the next period (M24 – M36), it has been agreed inside the project to continue the logical actions as next:

- 1) Concentrate in more relevant key actors to make them move towards the right-side of the graph, meaning their status of activation in respect BioRural and the ERBN improves.

Relevant and crucial key actors to be contacted to pass (at least) from...		
...inactive...		... to aware
Communication actions and meetings. Showing the value of BioRural ACTIONS		

...aware...		... to active	...showing the specific actions where they can get value
...active...		... to engaged	...offering to collaborate in actions of their high interest

- 2) As project evolves continue discovering new key actors that may be interested to be object of communication, to incorporate to the tracking

Specific details and highlights by each NE RBP country is presented below.

RBP NE: ERBN and adhesion of key actors and another stakeholders

In the initial planning set by NE RBP partners, it was set a target of achieving 60 key actors to be part of the ERBN community by end of August 2024 (BioRural project Month 24). The individual minimum target was set by country to reach at least 20 organisations enrolled by the mentioned date. This enrolment can take place and can be proved by:

- persons registering into the toolkit (key actors or stakeholders organisations)
- alternatively, under reception of a formal statement (email or letter) of their intend to collaborate with BioRural and the ERBN (mostly key actors).

At month M24 the achievements are summarised into Figure 18. As observed on the left side at M24 a total of 101 organisations have subscribed to the ERBN registered through the BioRural toolkit. This total of 101 organisations being part of the ERBN complies with the minimum target set of 60 organisations registered by M24. This shows an outstanding contribution from the NE RBP in the path to start growing the ERBN community..

Among these 101 organisations, 89 are key actors and 10 are stakeholders. The key actors have been object of direct communication and engagement for this purpose. Stakeholders, however, have subscribed as being reached by BioRural through communication (social media, posts, news, fairs, etc.) or after participating in any of BioRural actions (workshops, tutorials, events, etc.). This aggregation of key actors and stakeholders in connection through a platform, interested in innovation, bioeconomy and application of new small scale solutions, is a principal value which in return is expected to attract more organisations to enrol into the ERBN in the next period (by M36, August 2025).

As observed in Figure 18 (right) which depicts the distribution of the 101 organisations from NE RBP registered in the ERBN through the BioRural toolkit, at M24 associations, clusters, NGOs are prevailing whereas the remaining present a research and education government bodies or, private company being at the moment less numerous. This is the result of diverse strategies inside each NE RBP countries, with Latvia having larger share of research and education, though still incorporating other actors while Lithuania having a large number of private companies. As project develops and new actions in workshops take place, it is expected the share will change, including also larger amount of stakeholders, not only key actors.

Figure 18. NE RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M24. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile

2.5.2 Highlights by NE RBP country: Poland, Latvia and Lithuania

The general planning of the strategies for Poland, Latvia and Lithuania is available as an Annex to D2.1. Here a brief update and main highlights of the M24 status are presented.

POLAND

At M24 the total key actors identified adds a total of 163. A total of 133 key actors have been added in the period M12-M24, as they were new success cases (reported under T2.4) or necessary collaborators for the national workshops under T3.2 and for online workshops (T3.1). The distribution is as presented next in Figure 34 (left), with predominant profiles primary producers organisations, rural actors, companies and their organisations and research and education. At M24, as observed in Figure 34 (right) a total of 163 key actors have been approached, leading to 87 having already participated in at least one project action, and 23 of them having already collaborated, supporting BioRural implementation (e.g. as co-organiser of T3.2 workshops, or by bridging towards other organisations).

It is observed that the principal profiles active and collaborating are primary producers (individual farmers, foresters, fishers) and primary producers organisations as well as Consultant. The numbers have also improved (in respect M12) for other profiles, though in lower rate.

The development of subscriptions to the Toolkit and the European Rural Bioeconomy Platform will be continued. This is very important work to foster a collaborative environment that is continued at various levels. The cooperation with representatives of science and the advisor turned out to be the most fruitful. Despite not signing up to the toolkit, they disseminated information about the workshops taking place the most and enabled the spread of knowledge in the field of bioeconomy

LATVIA

At M24 the total key actors identified adds a total of 56. A total of 33 key actors have been added in the period M12-M24, as they were new success cases (reported under T2.4) or necessary collaborators for the national workshops under T3.2 and for online workshops (T3.1). The distribution is with predominant profiles of primary producers organisations, rural actors, companies and their organisations and research and education. At M24 a total of 56 key actors have been approached, leading to 29 having already participated in at least one project action, and 9 of them having already collaborated, supporting BioRural implementation (e.g. as co-organiser of T3.2 workshops, or by bridging towards other organisations).

In respect of ERBN subscription, target by M24 was initially set to 15 organisations. This figure already surpasses the M36 goal, with a total of 41 members adhered to ERBN community. At the current status, a total community of 41 users can be considered as part of ERBN, who have already subscribed through the toolkit.

The evolution after 2023 has expanded to other key actors necessary to organise the T3.1 workshops. As such several primary producers' organisations, consultation organisations, innovators and more research and education organisations were contacted and involved. The reaction was positive, but as well it was observed that new biobased solutions and circularity are welcomed and appreciated, but not priority, usually linked to the primary products production, prices and framework. This was further observed in march 2024, a period when the primary sector has been under demonstrations in Latvia. A week after the T3.1. workshops LBTU organised all 3 of the T3.2. national workshops bringing together various stakeholders and key actors who not only created new bio-based ideas, but also provided us and each other with additional contacts to expand the network.

LITHUANIA

At M24 the total key actors identified adds a total of 41. A total of 17 key actors have been added in the period M12-M24, as they were new success cases (reported under T2.4) or necessary collaborators for the regional workshops under T3.2 and for launching the EU Challenge (T3.3). The distribution is as presented next in Figure 1 (left), with predominant profiles companies and their organisations, research and education, and primary producers organisations. At M24, as observed in Figure 1 (right) a total of 26 key actors have been approached, leading to 39 representatives from the key actor institution having already participated in at least one project action, and 34 of them having already collaborated, supporting BioRural implementation (e.g. as co-organiser of T3.2 workshops, or by bridging towards other organisations).

The evolution of the involvement of key actors into project actions is well observed the quadrant graphs. It is there evident how the rightmost quadrants (meaning actors already engaged and collaborating) is more densely populated than the graph at M12. Notwithstanding the period M24 to M36 it must be reconsidered to invest efforts to involve key organisations either in project actions or into ERBN maintenance.

The National BioRural workshops helped to reach out those targeted stakeholders and increased their awareness and interest on BioRural project and its activities. It is clear that the key actors from academy, are more aware about the project initiatives as they are part of VMU and other academic community and the knowledge share is more efficient. However, private companies and individuals were targeted with a concrete invitations and proposals, guiding them to the subscription and explaining the ERBN, its benefits and rationale.

2.6 Aggregated indicators for all RBPs and ERBN

As result of the evolution of BioRural every RBP has grown an initial community of interest ready for supporting BioRural actions, and to get involved into the ERBN. The summary of the results achieved is presented next following a similar approach as done in previous sections for the RBPs. The aggregated numbers have been prepared as being informative of the size of engagement actions and ERBN community, and not intended for setting the strategies and actions, which are elaborated at RBP and national levels.

Summary of all RBPs: Key actors profile

As result of the identification of key actors being relevant for supporting BioRural actions, the aggregation of all countries is presented in Figure 19. Table 11 indicates the KPIs planned in general for the whole project, showing key actors profiles and the bioeconomy topics of interest.

As observed in Figure 19, at M24 the total key actors identified and which should be approached during the project adds **at the moment 1,131 organisations in the 4 RBPs together**. In respect the targeted key actors identified at M12, which added 887 organisations, **BioRural partners have in total identified in the period M12-M24 244 new key actors**. This increase of targeted key actors to be approached is logical and coherent, since the first draft of the national strategic plans prepared by partners were done during the first year (by M12), when still several relevant project actions had not started. During the period M12 – M24, as expected, partners have proceeded with the tasks

and connected with some of the targeted actors. But also have discovered others initially not considered, which have been participants or collaborators in this period.

The increase of the targeted key actors has been quite even among the different classes, and the distribution, as represented in Figure 19, is quite paired to the distribution in M12. In terms of the current volumes of key actors, partners have found relevant to involve primarily private sector of providers and adopters and their organisations (294) and research organisations (217), as being fundamental for the project actions. As well primary producers and their organisations (144) are a key target. Government (109) and rural organisations (78) are minor in number, but are crucial as a bridge and facilitators, as well as a backup to project actions. Therefore, their number do not imply less significance, as they are very influencing actors. Consultants and their organisations are potential actors interested as players in knowledge transfer adding 76 organisations. Networks (96) and projects (69) are also well represented, those in general having more direct links and readiness for cooperation.

Figure 19. BioRural RBPs: summary of key actors profiles for reinforcing BioRural and grow the ERBN during whole project.

In respect the bioeconomy topics covered by these key actors already identified, they are presented in Table 11. As observed the prevailing class Theme is “Agriculture and food” with a share of 23% of tags. The rest of bioeconomy topics range 10 to 15%, so quite balanced. The fact that #Agr/F is prominent topic is coherent with the reality in each RBP and by individual country, as agri-food sector is the principal bioeconomy sector in most of the countries. A relevant tag group is #Hor (Horizontal) with a 23% representing for example research organisations or rural organisations working horizontally in all topics. This adds representation to all bioeconomy tags.

Table 11. BioRural RBPs: Bioeconomy themes and strategy KPIs as planned at M24 of project

Period: M1-M36 Bioeconomy theme	TOTAL		Nr. By Profile								
	Nr	%	#PP or #PPOrg	#Comp or #Comp.Org	#Cons or #Cons.Org	#RU or #RU.Org	#Gov	#R/Ed	#Net	#Proj	#Oth
[Agr/F] Agri/F	299	23%	73	65	10	20	25	56	27	20	3
[For] Forest	127	10%	19	18	9	8	15	31	16	7	4
[Aq] Aquatic	180	14%	52	37	15	2	14	40	7	5	8
[BE] Bioenergy	155	12%	3	64	11	11	14	24	10	10	8
[BM] Biomaterials	192	15%	2	106	9	5	5	37	14	9	5
[Hor] Horizontal	250	19%	2	23	16	39	55	51	21	27	16
[Nspec] Non specific	85	7%	1	12	18	4	8	22	9	2	9
TOTAL (Nr)	1,288	100%	152	325	88	89	136	261	104	80	53
TOTAL (%)	100%	100%	12%	25%	7%	7%	11%	20%	8%	6%	4%

IMPORTANT NOTE: this table summarises the tags, to identify if all bioeconomy themes are being covered in the strategy to approach key actors. Since several key actors have been tagged with more than one tag, the total accounting of tags (1,288 tags) is larger than the total number of key actors (1,131).

Status of all RBPs at M24 (August 2024)

BioRural partners considered to prioritise the **engagement of key actors by M12, by concentrating in approaching 481 of the 887 initially detected**. However, BioRural actions expanded from M12 to M24, including among others impacting actions like more than 40 workshops, 5 EU online webinars, reporting of more than 20 success cases and launch of the EU Challenge in four regions. In consequence **partners have widen the target towards most of the key actors**, and this has led to even **increase the actors identified from 887 to 1,131**. For this stage it is considered any key actors was targeted.

The result of BioRural partners efforts in communication and engagement actions are presented in Table 12 and Figure 20. **Among the 1,131 key actors identified, 824 have been object of communication**, meaning 72% of the identified key actors are to some degree aware of BioRural purpose and strategy. The communication and engagement performed by partners has led to meet in a personal communication 542 actors, adding at least 738 meetings (on-site, on-line, phone or casual dialogues as result of networking in events). This has been instrumental to **lead 356 of these 1,131 actors (more than 30%) to participate** in project actions. **And in total 229 of them (20%) have collaborated** by supporting or co-organising project actions (303 individual collaborations). Notwithstanding from the total 1,131 key actors identified, 307 remain at the moment unaware of BioRural and the ERBN, or at least there is no evidence reported by partners. As such partners will evaluate the convenience to approach them, to expand to other new key actors, and/or to keep collaborating with already engaged actors towards M36.

Table 12. BioRural RBPs: Actions performed to approach key actors by M24

ACTIONS	Nr. KEY ACTORS		TOTAL NR of actions		Interpretation (figures at M24)
	M12	M24	M12	M24	
Communications	402	824	402	824	Communications are informative or “ice-breaking” contacts performed to make aware of BioRural exists, and its aims. But they are not engagement actions. <i>A total of 824 key actors have been object of communication with either emails or calls.</i>
Meetings	252	542	289	738	<u>Meetings are direct actions of engagement</u> (visits, in person talk, phone or e-meetings) where partners explain value and try to activate interest, so that key actors will take part into BioRural actions. <i>A total of 542 key actors approached, few of them with more than one meeting, totalling 738 meetings.</i>
Participations	166	356	181	470	<u>Participation refers to</u> take part in a project action, meaning key actors is active, but not meaning they are supporting project actions. Examples are: participate as audience in a seminar or workshop, respond a survey, etc. <i>A total of 356 key actors have participated in BioRural actions by M24. Several of them participated in more than one action (adding a total of 470 participations). Among these 356 key actors, 164 of them have also collaborated, meaning that 192 can be considered active, but not still engaged (see Figure 4).</i>
Collaborations	80	229	87	303	<u>Collaboration means</u> that engagement has been successful to trigger key actors to support BioRural actions: by collaborating in organising a workshop, by engaging other stakeholders to participate in project surveys, etc. <i>A total of 229 key actors have collaborated with BioRural. Several of them collaborated not just once, and therefore 303 collaborations took place.</i>

These figures are also displayed visually and disaggregated in Figure 20 by key actor profile.

Figure 20. BioRural RBPs: status of activation of key actors at M24. LEFT: Targeted VS Achieved contacts. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor

As observed in Figure 20 (left) during the period M12-M24 the RBP partners faced to potentially contact and or engage the whole set of identified key actors (totaling 1,131). **Partners have finally approached** (aware, active or engaged) **849 of them by M24**. The remaining 282 actors identified (in each country) will be object to consideration during period M24-M36, to optimise project results. This may lead, for example, to realise several key actors initially thought to be targeted, to not be relevant anymore, and thus to steer the strategy accordingly in collaborations with key actors already engaged and resulting strategical for the successful implementation of BioRural actions.

As relevant project actions took place several participations and collaborations were being triggered. Among the 1,131 key actors object of contact for awareness, **a total of 421 (37%) have already participated and/or collaborated**, meaning:

- 192 key actors have participated, but not collaborated; thus they reach the status of “active”
- 229 actors have collaborated, meaning they reached the status of “engaged” with BioRural. It must be noted that several of these actors, 164 in total, have done both, participate and collaborate. Notwithstanding in terms of degree of engagement they are classified with the superior stage, “engaged”.

Summary of all RBPs: ERBN and adhesion of key actors and another stakeholders

In the initial planning it was set a target of achieving 20 members per country to be part of the ERBN community by end of August 2024 (BioRural project Month 24). This implied to reach a total of 280 persons registered affiliated either to a key actor organisation or to a stakeholder organisation. This enrolment has taken place by:

- persons registering into the toolkit
- alternatively, under reception of a formal statement (email or letter) of their intend to collaborate with BioRural and the ERBN

At month M12 a total of 233 users had either subscribed or declared intend to be part of ERBN. At the current **M24 the membership has grown**, as presented in Figure 18, **to 472 members**, 432 through the toolkit registration and 40 of them through a formal statement. This total membership is **192 persons above the target of 280 set by M24** (end of August 2024). The membership has been performed by t registering into BioRural toolkit, or by providing a formal communication of intend.

Among these 472 members, 338 are affiliated to key actors organisations, whereas 134 to stakeholders organisations. The key actors have been object of direct communication and engagement for this purpose. Stakeholders, however, have subscribed as being reached by BioRural through communication (social media, posts, news, fairs, etc.) or after participating in any of BioRural actions (workshops, tutorials, events, etc.). This aggregation

of key actors and stakeholders in connection through a platform, interested in innovation, bioeconomy and application of new small scale solutions, is a principal value which in return is expected to attract more organisations to enrol into the ERBN in the next period (by M36, August 2025).

Figure 21 depicts the distribution of the 472 ERBN members. The distribution shows that the principal group are companies (from 61 members in M12 to 179 members in M24) followed by Research and Education (from 60 members in M12 to 124 in M24). Members from associations and clusters (both sectorial and primary producers organisations) have grown from 35 to 95. Government and other profiles have grown to a lesser extent, from 18 to 34 in case of Government and Public Administrations, and from 25 to 36 in the case of other profiles. All in all, this brings together principally companies (either technological or from primary sector), their organisations, and research and education, are together the key actors necessary to promote collaborations and further transfer and uptake of new bio-based circular solutions.

Figure 21. BioRural ERBN: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M24. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile

3 Area of action #2. Bioeconomy networks and projects

3.1 Introduction

BioRural aims to embrace synergies with thematic networks, multi-actor projects and EC services. The aim is to achieve far-reaching dissemination and exploitation, to better facilitate the cross-border transfer of regional bio-based solution applications, and to establish durable collaborations in such action lines, complementing and reinforcing other EU structures and channels.

For that purpose, it is crucial to establish contact and synergies with other networks and projects. In case of networks, those that complement BioRural work and value, or other networks that partially overlap in purpose or functions. In both cases to generate more impact and more reach by combining actions or sharing materials. BioRural has established two action lines for this purpose.

- Creation of a new permanent collaborative structure: this has been organized around the recently created RBA – Rural Bioeconomy Alliance, a cluster of European funded projects which come together to share knowledge on project outcomes and support dissemination and communication activities related to existing knowledge of the bioeconomy. BioRural performs the connection with the RBA projects through CERTH as project coordinator and by FSH as communication leader. Individual partners are establishing synergies at local level, when any of the RBA projects operates in their country as well.
- Individual interaction of BioRural with other EU and national bioeconomy research projects and networks:
 - Projects: either EU or national, they are temporal environments of collaboration of organizations, which are, at least some of them, key actors for BioRural. These projects, when aligned with BioRural vision and objectives, offer the possibility to establish punctual or temporary collaborations to achieve wider impacts, either at EU or at national level.
 - Networks: either EU or national, offer the possibility to reinforce BioRural's reach, by complementing actions, or by facilitating access to a wider public. These networks, refer principally to national and EU networks like CAP Networks, or Rural Development Networks. But beyond these formal networks, other networks specific on bioeconomy, sustainable farming, agri-food innovation and transfer, etc. are potential allies for BioRural either at EU or at national level.

Both forms of liaison have been explored by BioRural partners. The steps performed in respect the RBA activation, and the identified projects and networks are presented in next sub-sections 3.2 and 3.3 respectively.

3.2 The Rural Bioeconomy Alliance – RBA

3.2.1 About RBA

The Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA) is a cluster of European funded projects that support the development of rural sustainable circular bioeconomy initiatives in the EU with action lines such as: analyse framework, rural circular bioeconomy success stories, best practices, pilots as well as ways (e.g. training and education) to increase the adoption of circular bioeconomy concepts mainly in rural areas.

By creating such a cluster it is enhanced the impact on supporting the transition towards a circular bioeconomy beyond the effects achievable by individual projects. These projects come together to share knowledge on project outcomes and support dissemination and communication activities related to existing knowledge of the bioeconomy. The cluster project has agreed to collaborate to promote joint actions, knowledge sharing and synergies as next: (i) events organisation and dissemination / promotion; (ii) exchange of success stories contents and lessons learned; (iii) exchange insights on small-scale biobased innovative technologies; (iv) workshops co-organisation and promotion; (v) knowledge exchange among projects and to a wider audience; (vi) reinforced dissemination of projects' results

3.2.2 RBA members and coordination

The RBA coordination is taken over by different project partners on a 6 month rotation. BioRural through CERTH initiated the RBA and led it for the first 6 months (15 May- 15 November 2023). The second period was led by MainstreamBIO through Q-Plan (15 November 2023 - 15 May 2024). The third and current period is led by CEE2ACT through GEONARDO. The RBA coordinator is in charge of organising and hosting regular virtual meetings of all project representatives, and leading any other tasks that are required to keep the RBA relevant and active. The RBA is currently going through an expansion whereby a number of additional projects, in addition to the 11 below, will be accepted into the alliance.

Figure 22. Rural Bioeconomy Alliance – RBA: logo and participating projects at date August 2024

3.2.3 Results – Status at M24

At M9 the RBA was invited to and launched on the 31st of May 2023 at the COOPID Bioeconomy Conference in Brussels. Since then, regular internal meetings between Alliance members have allowed partners to share relevant knowledge, events and explore synergies. Over the past year, the Alliance has been represented at various high-level events including the Regional Innovation Valleys for Bioeconomy and Food Systems (RIV4BFS), the EC Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival and the World Circular Economy Forum. In addition, the RBA has been represented and presented at a range of national workshops held by RBA members.

In the coming months, planning is ongoing for the RBA to be represented at various events. In addition, various initiatives are underway to collaborate on developing joint policy recommendations for accelerating the transition to a circular bioeconomy. It is expected that a range of newly funded projects will join the RBA in the coming year.

3.3 Liaison with national and EU projects

Liaising with projects is part of BioRural strategy for reaching more impactful results and to further widen the project reach to diverse stakeholders. Projects are temporary initiatives, with programs of actions counting on with specific budgets to execute them. The collaboration with projects, either at EU or at national scales, is therefore a path to reach more impact in the actions programmed under BioRural.

The liaison with projects is presented below, arranged as next:

1. **The RBA – Rural bioeconomy alliance:** as a collaborative framework for EU funded projects on rural bioeconomy
2. **Long term EU initiatives:** projects that may facilitate not only individual synergies, but the integration of BioRural results, ERBN and BioRural toolkit with/into other referential EU scale structures and initiatives

3. **EU funded projects**, contemporary and similar to BioRural, with 2 to 4 years duration, and having similar scopes and targets, thus allowing collaborations at EU Level (in webinars, EU events, etc.) and at national level (local or regional workshops, surveys, etc.) when the projects have programmed actions in the same country
4. **National projects**, which may allow synergies at local or national level in a specific country by the interaction of a specific partner with projects like Operational groups, national R&D projects, operating only at national or local scale

BioRural partners have contributed through task T2.1 and T2.2 to establish contact and collaborations with other EU and also national projects. Multiple synergies have taken place. At the moment of month M24 a total of 29 individual collaborations took effect between partners of BioRural and RBA projects, thus connecting and reinforcing BioRural and the 11 RBA projects.

Additionally a total of three long term EU initiatives have been identified: EU-Farmbook, modernAKIS and Tools4CAP. The main synergy has taken place with EU-Farmbook including a collaboration and an agreement to connect BioRural toolkit with EU-Farmbook.

Partners have identified at M24 a total of 24 EU project and 8 national projects to establish synergies with. About EU projects, a total of 48 lines of collaboration were discussed, achieving 29 collaborations taking place already by M24. In respect the national funded projects, a total of 8 (2 more than at M12) have been identified. From the 17 potential lines of collaboration, a total of 9 synergies occurred by M24.

3.3.1 Liaison with RBA projects

The RBA projects cluster (as presented in section 3.2) network has already started the collaboration among project coordinators and dissemination leaders. At country level synergies have already being detected and planned by BioRural partners.

Among the 11 RBA projects, synergies have been established with all of them. Among these 11 projects BioRural and other 9 projects are still ongoing, whereas COOPID finished in June 2023. Already 29 individual collaborations have taken place already. Notwithstanding partners have already identified at least 37 lines of collaboration, and therefore more synergies are expected to take place during the third year of the project.

Table 13. Series to tables to track synergies with the RBA projects

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	COOPID (Jan 2021-June 2023)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM, #BE	WEB	Spanish Agrifood Cooperatives	Bioeconomy cluster, innovative business model, primary production, knowledge transfer, peer-to-peer dissemination
Project description: The reduction of CO2 emissions and an overall lower waste production chain hinge on the successful uptake of sustainable bio-based business models in the primary production sector. The EU-funded COOPID project is proposing a new strategy. A network of COOPID Bioeconomy Clusters from 10 European countries has been created ad hoc, involving a range of stakeholders: primary producers, in cooperatives or associations, within agriculture, forestry and aquaculture; industry; public sector; research and academia. Based on the proposed model, COOPID ambassadors will showcase success stories, organise workshops and conduct interactive dissemination and communication campaigns. One of the main target groups will be women and young producers who have great potential to innovate but are underrepresented in the primary production sector					
Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece / Finished					
Synergy planned: (i) dissemination of BioRural and RBA during COOPID final project conference					
Achieved: (i) CERTH presented newly created RBA platform and BioRural during the Final COOPID Conference (31 st may 2023, #EUGreenWeek 2023 Partner Event, at Les Ateliers des Tanneurs, Brussels).					

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	MainstreamBIO (Oct 2022-Sept2025)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM	WEB	QPlan	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

Project description:

The objective of MainstreamBIO is to foster small-scale bio-based projects in rural areas, in order to promote the participation of more actors in the development of the bioeconomy. The project will offer tailor-made technical and business support tools and services, designed in collaboration with Multi-Stakeholder Innovation Platforms (MIPs), to rural actors in the participating regions leading small-scale bioeconomy initiatives.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / SPAIN / identified and partially implemented

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events/workshops. (ii) Support to project visualisation. (iii) Collaboration in the European Challenge in Spain

Achieved: (iii) INNOVARUM (Spanish partner of MainstreamBio) shared T3.3 EU challenge with bioeconomy community of interest in Ebro Valley region (June 2024)

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece / Ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) connecting MainstreamBio and BioRural candidates for mutual calls; (ii) Potential joined policy workshop in May/June 2025

Achieved: (i) mutual support in finding candidates for MainstreamBIO's open call for Central Macedonia and BioRural Eu challenge SE regional call (T3.3)

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland / participating

Synergy planned: (i) mutual support in dissemination; (ii) co-organisation of events and workshops, (iii) common final event (e.g), (iv) round table,

Achieved: (i) IUNG partner shared T3.3 EU challenge with bioeconomy community of interest in (June 2024), distribution of brochures at their workshops. Including information about BioRural at presentations during their meetings. (ii) Partners from MaistreamBIO have presented their work at workshop organised within T3.1

Partner / country / status: Delphy / The Netherlands / linked

Synergy planned: (i) mutual support in and presenting their project work at workshops and events; (ii) support to project visualization (iii) Collaboration towards the European Challenge in the Netherlands

Achieved: participating in ERBN, participating in organized events and workshops. Shared communication on workshops and results.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	CEE2ACT	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM	WEB	Geonardo Ltd	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

Project description:

CEE2ACT is empowering countries in Central Eastern Europe and beyond (Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia and Slovenia) to develop circular bioeconomy strategies and action plans through innovative governance models. The objective is to achieve better informed decision-making processes, societal engagement and innovation, building on the practice of partners from contributing countries (Austria, Germany, The Netherlands, Belgium, Spain, Finland, Sweden), and addressing relevant economic, social and environmental aspects. The project will also create bioeconomy hubs to facilitate the transfer of knowledge and to develop a participatory, non-political, bottom-up approach.

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland / participating

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops, (ii) common final event (e.g)

Achieved: (i) Partners from CEE2ACT have presented their work at workshop organised within T3.1

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece/

Synergy planned: Future synergy.

Achieved: No synergy achieved to date

Partner / country / status: GEA /ASIMCOV / ROMANIA / discussed, close cooperation.

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops. (II) Support to project visualisation. (III) Joint event in Q4 of 2023 with the support of the Sustainable Development Department of the Government of Romania.

Achieved: (i) co-organised a workshop on capacity building and knowledge transfer in May 2024. (iii) organized joint event in Q4 of 2023 with the support of the Sustainable Development Department of the Government of Romania, jointly participated in the bioeconomy session in the Clusters meet Regions in Iasi, in November 2023 together with other RBA projects.

Partner / country / status: UL, Algen / Slovenia/ close cooperation with the Anteja (Partner in CEE2ACT, contact for Bioeconomy hub in Slovenia <https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/slovenia/>).

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops. (ii) Supporting dissemination; (iii) further collaborations

Achieved: (i) Participation in two national multi-actor innovation workshops. (iii) UL has been invited to CEE2Act Bioeconomy HUB Slovenia

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	RuralBioUp (October 2022 - September 2025)	#Ag, #For, #BM	WEB	APRE	Bioeconomy, biobased, circular economy

Project description:

The aim of the RuralBioUp project is to bring together the players in an area in order to develop the use of bio-based resources on a local scale. RuralBioUp also seeks to develop and structure the bioeconomy sectors in the territories. It will strengthen the cooperation among regional key actors and knowledge holders in order to support bio-based business models in rural areas. In particular, RuralBioUp will establish nine regional hubs across six EU countries that will co-design and implement nine action plans on 18 value chains. Those areas will be empowered by RuralBioUp's partners with mentoring, coaching and training activities in the implementation of their action plans. A digital tool, the RuralBioUp One-Stop-Shop, will support regional actors in making science-based decisions. By mapping the players and their needs beforehand, the project will develop a platform for pooling solutions and cooperation between local players (e.g. producers of by-products and innovators of bio-based solutions).

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE / agreed.

Achieved: (i) Agreement to disseminate BioRural events and actions (ii) communication to the RuralBio Up and Scale Up network of ERBN and registrations.

Partner / country / status: CERTH/ Greece /ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Involvement of BioRural members in validation of RuralBioUp platform; (ii) Future synergies under discussion.

Achieved: (i) Members of BioRural were invited and participated in RuralBioUp's platform validation focus group in Iasi, Romania on November 21st 2023.

Partner / country / status: GEA / ROMANIA / discussed, close cooperation

Synergy planned: (i) visualisation of mutual actions (ii) Potential joint workshops on inland raw materials topic (agriculture, forestry) (iii) Joint event in Q4 of 2023 with the support of the Sustainable Development Department of the Government of Romania.

Achieved: (iii) jointly participated in the bioeconomy session in the Clusters meet Regions in Iasi, in November 2023 together with other RBA projects.

Partner / country / status: CBE/ Portugal/ First contact performed

Institute for Economic Forecasting – Romanian Academy/

Synergy planned: Future synergy. In the process of scheduling a meeting to discuss potential actions.

Achieved: No further synergy achieved

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	SCALE-UP (September 2022- August 2025)	#Ag, #For, #BM	WEB	ECO	Bioeconomy, biobased, circular economy

Project description:

The overall objective of SCALE-UP is to support regional multi-stakeholder partnerships, comprising private companies, public authorities, civil society organisations and researchers, to identify and develop innovative and sustainable value chains based on regional biomass resources. Through its approach, SCALE-UP will adapt, implement and evaluate tools to help regional actors overcome apparent bottlenecks to fully exploit the potential of the bioeconomy in their region. SCALE-UP will support regional multi-actor partnerships, consisting of private businesses, governments and policymakers, civil society organizations, and researchers in identifying and scaling-up innovative and sustainable bio-based value chains that build on regional resources.

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE / agreed

Achieved: (i) Agreement to disseminate BioRural events and actions (ii) communication to the RuralBioUp and Scale Up network of ERBN and registrations.

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece/ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) mutual dissemination of project actions; (ii) Future synergies under discussion.

Achieved: (i) Disseminated SCALE-UP request to look for relevant local biobased value chains that would be relevant for mentoring support.

Partner / country / status: Green Growth Platform / North Macedonia/ Synergy agreed upon

Synergy planned: Participation in events/workshops. Collaboration in stakeholders mapping and engagement in the south-eastern parts of The Republic of North Macedonia.

Achieved: Participation in online knowledge exchange workshops by an invitation of SDEWES center – North Macedonia (SCALE UP project partner). Collaborative meeting and activities for the purposes of key stakeholders mapping in the rural bio-economy.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM/ Spain / First contact performed

Synergy planned: (i) potential connection of BioRural success case with SCALE-UP workshops; (ii) Potential participation in workshops; (iii) Mutual dissemination.

Achieved: (iii) communication in social networks and distribution of SW EU challenge opportunity

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	Biomodel4regions (July 2022-June 2025)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM	WEB	Ciaotech	Bioeconomy, biobased, network

Project description:

The BIOMODEL4REGIONS project aims to support the establishment of the innovative governance models at local/regional level to achieve better-informed decision-making processes, social engagement and innovation to support and strengthen EU and international science-policy interfaces to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals.

Partner / country / status: NaturePlast / FRANCE / participating

Synergy planned: (i) Share network and pool the effects.

Achieved: (i) Discussions have been initiated with a view to presenting the two projects at French workshops, as well as monitoring and promoting both projects on social networks.

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece / pending

Synergy planned: pending

Achieved: No synergy achieved to date

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	P2GreeN (Dec 2022-Nov 2026)	#Ag, #BE #BM	WEB	Agrathaer GMBH	-Air and water pollution control - Fertilization - Wastewater management

Project description:

P2GreeN will foster a paradigm shift, from a linearly organized resource and nutrient system within the agri-food supply chain, towards a circular material flow system between urban and rural areas thereby restoring the coupling of the water-agri-food system using a holistic symbiotic resource management approach following the 3R principle "Reduce, Reuse, Recover". P2GreeN will therefore develop new circular governance solutions for the transition from fork to farm to halt and eliminate N & P pollution by connecting blue urban with green rural infrastructure, focusing on circular nutrient flows of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P).

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) mutual collaboration in events and workshops. (ii) Support to project visualisation. (iii) Collaboration towards the European Challenge in Greece

Achieved: (i) Presented the BioRural toolkit to coordinators as an example of best practice.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
ERASMUS-LS	RELIEF (June 2022-May 2025)	#BE, #Agr	WEB	UoP	bio economy, sustainable development, circular economy, digitalization, agriculture, green skills, entrepreneurial skills, transversal skills, digital skills

Project description:

RELIEF aims to develop and deliver an innovative approach for teaching bio-economy in farming, by developing specific learning resources addressing HEIs students and farming practitioners. HEIs, VETs, farmer consultants, research institutes, and social partners from Italy, Greece, Sweden, Cyprus and Portugal will deliver a high-quality network within the EU to advance bio-economy in the farming agenda. RELIEF will deliver a training needs analysis and develop two curricula in bio-economy, for HE students, farming practitioners and farmers exploring the key areas that are critical for the implementation of business models and strategies towards bio-economy in farming. Based on this knowledge, RELIEF will design and pilot learning units which will incorporate a mix of training methodologies.

Partner / country / status: CERTH/ Greece / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) visualisation of mutual actions. (ii) Potential workshop on inland resources. (iii) Synergies on European Challenge.

Achieved: (i) Relief project was presented in the Greek National Aquatics Workshop

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon 2020	ShapingBio (Sep 2022-Aug 2025)	#BE, #Agr	WEB	FRAUNHOFER Institut	Food system bioeconomy governance

Project description:

ShapingBio: aims to support and accelerate such an ecosystem. To that end, it will map and analyse initiatives, structures, policy instruments, gaps in policy and governance, applied R&D and technology transfer, as well as collaboration and financing across the EU

macro-regions and fields. It will work with stakeholders from various sectors and receive input from key actors. The results will lead to evidence-based and concrete information and recommendations for better policy-making and stakeholder activity. Moreover, it will support the EU Green Deal policy priorities and the EU's climate ambition for 2030 and beyond.

Partner / country / status: CERTH/ Greece / pending

Synergy planned: Future synergy.

Achieved: No synergy achieved to date

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM/Spain / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) participation in ShapingBio cross sectorial workshops. (ii) Dissemination of T3.3 EU Challenge.

Achieved: (i) AVEBIOM invited by AseBio (Spanish partner) and participated in cross-sectorial workshops online #1 (nov. 2023) and #3 (June 2024). (ii) T3.3 EU Challenge call SW shared by AseBio to local community of interest for ShapingBio.

Partner / country / status: IUNG/Poland/ongoing

Synergy planned: participation in ShapingBio cross sectorial workshops.

Achieved: IUNG invited by APRE (Italian partner) and participated in cross-sectorial workshops online #1 (nov. 2023) # onsite (18th of April).

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	Robin (Sep 2022-Aug 2025)	#Agr, #BE	WEB	QPLAN	-government systems, bioeconomy

Project description:

ROBIN aims to empower Europe's regions to adapt their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts.

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece/ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) dissemination of project activities; (ii) Future synergies under discussion.

Achieved: (i) Robin partners disseminated BioRural's open calls during their workshop on July 18th 2024.

3.3.2 Liaison with long term EU initiatives

Three principal long-term initiatives have been identified and approached by M24 by BioRural partners: EU-FarmBook, modernAKIS and Tools4CAP. EU-Farmbook and ModernAKIS started 2022 and will be ongoing till 2029. They are both long term initiatives with potential continuation after 2029. In the case of Tools4CAP, the framework is Dezember 2026, still covering whole lifetime of BioRural. Specifically about them:

- EU-Farmbook covers 18 EU countries, to compile and facilitate practical knowledge for farmers and foresters in multilanguage environment. There is a high synergy for mutual benefits, as for example, BioRural can provide specific insights into small scale biobased solutions, and reversely, BioRural toolkit may be connected with EU-Farmbook (thus allowing to be better known and acknowledged).
- modernAKIS is empowering and structuring the AKIS system in 26 EU countries. Therefore collaboration is a path to visualise ERBN and BioRural toolkit to potential users or participants like AKIS bodies or agricultural advisors.
- Tools4CAP works in 17 EU countries to support the design and monitoring of national CAP strategic plans. The creation of a networking platform and the connection with CAP key actors per country is a potential synergy to connect BioRural and the newly created ERBN

Table 14. Series to tables to track synergies with Long term EU Initiatives

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HORIZON EUROPE	EU-FarmBook (August 2022-July 2029)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM, #BE	WEB	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	bioeconomy, digitalization, resources, platform, knowledge transfer

Project description:

EU-FarmBook, is a Horizon Europe project that is working at regional, national, and European level, to build a Digital Platform, gathering and sharing agriculture and forestry knowledge, based on a co-creation approach and built on EURAKNOS and EUREKA outputs. EU-FarmBook is the answer to real needs of farmers, foresters and advisors. The Horizon Europe project offers an interactive, multi-lingual meeting place for agriculture and forestry communities, giving access to trustworthy knowledge objects according to findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data principles. EU-FarmBook users can interact and explore innovative ways to solve their daily challenges.

Partner / status: AVEBIOM & CERTH / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Promotion of EU-Farmbook launch among RBA members and BioRural partners. (ii) Connect EU-Farmbook and BioRural toolkit

Achieved: (i) EU-Farmbook launch shared with RBA and BioRural partners; (ii) Agreement to connect EU-farmbook with BioRural toolkit (dependent of funding availability)

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HORIZON EUROPE	modernAKIS (Sept 2022-Aug 2029)	#Hor	WEB	LFI OSTERREICH	AKIS, support service, knowledge transfer

Project description:

modernAKIS, modernisation of Agriculture through more efficient and effective Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), aims to improve AKIS actors' capacities to leverage individual, organizational and systemic resources needed for the transformation towards more coherent, effective, and efficient AKIS systems and the transition to a more sustainable management and use of natural resources in farming and forestry.

To this end it will build and foster a European network of at least 1.000 key AKIS actors, including AKIS coordination bodies, from all EU MS, who will act as linchpins in the transformation of the AKIS systems towards a more effective governance and the modernization of the European agri-food sector.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / Spain / established contact

Synergy planned: discussed about synergies between ERBN and modernAKIS. (i) Agreed to transfer to modernAKIS partners and community to join ERBN once set-up and in operation. (ii) Potential key actors for ERBN management

Achieved: at the moment waiting for ERBN further consolidation and to strengthen the mutual relations

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HORIZON EUROPE	Tools4CAP (Jan 2023-Dez 2026)	#Hor	WEB	ECORYS BRUSSELS NV	CAP Strategic Plan, policy modelling, participatory approach

Project description:

Tools4CAP, which stands for Innovative Toolbox empowering effective CAP governance towards EU ambitions, is a Coordination and Support Action in Horizon Europe (2023-2026) coordinated by Ecorys, gathering 21 partner organisations.

The project aims to support the design and monitoring of the national Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Strategic Plans (SPs) 2023-2027 and lay the foundations for sound preparation of Post-2027 Strategic Plans through a bottom-up adaptation of innovative methods and tools. Tools4CAP ambition is to provide end users with suitable tools for a more evidence-based policy design, ultimately improving capabilities to design next-generation Strategic Plans and to perform monitoring tasks.

Partner / country / status: UL/ Slovenia / established contact

Synergy planned: still not discussed

Achieved: no synergy achieved so far

3.3.3 Liaison with EU funded projects

EU funded projects have been identified by BioRural partners to establish individual bilateral collaborations, mainly at country level. At M12 partners reported a total of 16 EU projects, for which a total of 11 agreed upon collaboration, and 6 had started the discussions to collaborate. At M24 partners have identified 8 EU projects more to establish synergies, thus adding 24 EU projects. At the moment BioRural partners have discussed and planned at least 48 individual lines of collaboration, leading to 29 collaborations taking place already by M24.

Table 15. Series to tables to track synergies with EU funded projects

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Interreg-CE	BIOECO-UP at a glance (04.2023-03.2026)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM	WEB	Ministry of Agriculture Hungary	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

The bioeconomy concept seeks to replace fossil resources with renewable raw materials in as many areas and applications as possible. The BIOECO-UP project widely establishes this concept across central Europe. The partners will design new circular value chains for the bioeconomy and change consumer behaviour. They will also support the policy level to push ahead with the transformation.

Partner / country / status: UL / Slovenia / participating as Partner

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops, (ii) common final event, (iii) mutual support in dissemination

Achieved: (i) participation in three national multi-actor innovation workshops, (iii) dissemination of project results and actions

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HORIZON 2020	BRANCHES (January 2020-Dec 2023)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM, #BE	WEB	LUKE Natural Resources Institute Finland	bioeconomy, knowledge transfer, thematic networks

Project description:

BRANCHES aims to promote the implementation of new cost-effective technologies; mobilize more biomass and create innovative business opportunities in rural areas by improving and strengthening the links between bioeconomy practice and science. The project will ensure communication through the two-way flow of information for the transfer of ideas and technologies between scientists and professionals from agriculture and forestry in rural areas. The valuable knowledge produced by research and development should always be shared far beyond the scientific community.

BRANCHES will integrate selected knowledge on forest and agricultural biomass supply chains with available innovative technologies and best practice cases for bioeconomy solutions with bioenergy conversion systems in a wider bioeconomy context. Five national thematic networks launched by BRANCHES in Germany, Poland, Finland, Italy and Spain will engage science and practitioners.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / Spain / agreed, started

Synergy planned: (i) presentation in mutual events. (ii) Potential invitation to IntercamBIOM national network to join ERBN. (iii) Participation in BRANCHES final event.

Achieved: (i) BioRural presentation 26th April 2023 at BRANCHES local workshop and visit to success case Alcarrás Bioproductors; (ii) two communication to the 400 members of IntercamBIOM (a. to announce BioRural Toolkit and ERBN; b. on SW EU Challenge); (iii) poster at BRANCHES final event Spain; (iii) presenting BioRural recommendations at BRANCHES final conference (Nov 2023, Rome)

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece&EU / discussed and finished

Synergy planned: (i) potential participation in RBA. (ii) Potential connection of the 5 NTNs created by BRANCHES with the ERBN and toolkit.

Achieved: Connections were offered. At the moment no further synergy achieved (BRANCHES project already finished Dez 2023).

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
ERASMUS-KA2	COM (June 2022-May 2025)	#BE, #Agr		UPV	bio economy, organic waste, sustainable development, circular economy, digitalization, green skills

Project description:

COM (Circular Organic Management) aims to develop and deliver a series of materials and tools for secondary school teachers to incorporate the circular economy into their classrooms, and more specifically on issues around organic waste management. Its goal is to support the behavioural change in schools around the food and organic waste, by engaging a set of actors, including teachers, students, schools, universities and social partners from Spain, Italy, Greece, Romania, Slovenia and Turkey.

Partner / country / status: ICO / Greece / established synergy

Synergy planned: Material developed in COM will be uploaded in BioRural Toolkit.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Interreg VI B	ReNu2Cycle (March 2023-March 2027)	#Agr, #BM		IZES gGmbH	Bio-based, recycled fertiliser

Project description:

The aim of ReNu2Cycle is to implement recycling derived fertilizer (short RDFs) to the market and thereby reduce the dependency on conventional fertiliser, which are optimized for the fast release of nutrients, making them an attractive choice for farmers but also a threat to soil and ecosystem. To address the implementation of RDFs to the market, ReNu2Cycle develops policy recommendations at regional and European level and is also testing various RDFs on pot and field trials in several North-West European Countries. The integral part of ReNu2Cycle is to develop RDF business solutions and technologies for a market uptake.

Partner / country / status: IZES gGmbH / Germany / agreed

Synergy planned: Introduction of technologies and project results into toolkit.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Interreg A	W.A.V.E. (proposal 2 step)	#BM	WEB	IZES gGmbH (Scientific)	Biomaterials, Forest Wood

Project description:

WaVE focuses on the improvement of regional and local policies to open up their possibilities for supporting the development of integrated adaptive reuses of water-linked cultural heritage sites in human settlements.

WaVE goal is to improve the overall support by the addressed policy instruments for integrated valorisation approaches of cultural heritage, to sparkle ideas for the creation of new projects aiming at integrated valorisation of water-linked cultural heritage, and to raise awareness for the subject at other cities and regions in Europe.

Partner / country / status: IZES gGmbH / Germany / proposal 2 step

Synergy planned: Introduction of technologies and project results into toolkit.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon 2020	Go-Grass (2022-2025)	#Ag, #BE	WEB	ATB	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

Project description:

The GO-GRASS project is developing small-scale bio-based solutions to unlock the overlooked potential of grassland across Europe and create new business opportunities for rural areas. To develop cost-effective and circular business models exploiting the underused potential of grass resources, GO-GRASS partners will test a wide range of solutions in four promising regional demonstration sites located in The Netherlands, Sweden, Germany and Denmark.

Partner / country / status: AU/ Denmark / identified - ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops. (ii) Support to project visualisation. (iii) Collaboration towards the Green Transition in Europe

Achieved: (i) Participation in national workshop on biomass. (iii) Results from Go-Grass provided input on exercises on innovation idea regarding protein extraction from biomass.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	B-Resilient (September 2022 - September 2025)	#Ag, #BM	WEB	Wagralim	Bioeconomy, co-product, circular economy,

Project description:

The B-Resilient project aims to increase the use of available raw materials and the recovery of secondary flows into biobased ingredients. In particular, it will enable SMEs involved in the production and processing of food products to become more resilient by making optimum use of biomass.

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE / discussed.

Synergy planned: (i) Looking for bioeconomy promotion, engagement, identification of actors and dissemination

Achieved: first discussions took place, no synergy achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	Blue Bio Cluster (September 2022 - September 2025)	#Aq	WEB	Submariner Network	Blue economy, blue bioeconomy, circular economy,

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE / discussed.

Synergy planned: (i) Looking for bioeconomy promotion, engagement, identification of actors and dissemination (ii) Co-organisation of events and workshops.

Achieved: first discussions took place, no synergy achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Intereg project	INdiGo (Sept 2022-Dec 2025)	#Aq, #BM	WEB	UBS University	Biodegradable plastics, marine environment, fishing gear

Project description:

The INdiGO project aims to develop the first fishing gear with a controlled lifespan that is biodegradable in the marine environment. It also aims to define a strategy for improving the recycling of end-of-life fishing gear and promoting the circular economy.

Partner / country / status: NaturePlast/ FRANCE / discussed

Synergy planned: (i) Share network and pool the effects. (ii) Some partners of this project will be asked to join the network.

Achieved: Discussions have begun with the project's French partners to enable them to join the toolkit. The INdiGO project is now finished.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
ERASMUS +	SAGRE (June 2021-Nov 2023)	#Agr	WEB	Republic of Turkey - Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry -General Directorate of Agrarian Reform	*Precision agriculture *Circular economy *Sustainable agriculture

Project description:

SAGRE purposes two issues on farming and specifically on the crop and horticulture cultivation

- to enhance the precise and sustainable usage of chemical fertilizers
- to promote a shift to Circular Economy and increased usage of bio-fertilizers

SAGRE trains the trainers. SAGRE builds on the excellence of European agri-technology and directs its efforts on transferring knowledge and demonstrating feasible IT solutions to build capacity for the new profession of Smart Agri Expert. Smart Agri Experts will form a practice-oriented knowledge node between agri-tech forerunners, science community and agriculture stakeholders and farmers.

Partner / country / status: Green Growth Platform / North Macedonia/ finished

Synergy planned: (i) Participation in events and workshops; (ii) collaboration in field of precise agriculture.

Achieved: (i) Representatives of AgFutura Technologies (SAGRE project partner) took active participation in all of the national capacity building workshops (T3.2) and gave a presentation on their Remote Agriculture Monitoring and Advisory System (RAMAS) at the online knowledge exchange workshop on food and agriculture (T3.1).

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Europe	Locality (June 2023 – May 2026)	#Ag, #Aq, #BM	not yet established	NIVA	Algae, food, agriculture, aquaculture

Project description:

LOCALITY will implement local, innovative, and sustainable value chains, supporting the interaction of the algae value chain actors with relevant waste stream producing industries. Three regional ecosystems will be strategically developed in key regions considering strong and active business on which circularity and sustainability will be improved by the reutilization of wasted nutrients for algae cultivation. An integrative methodology involving R&D partners, industry, and SMEs will work in each market sector to develop innovative and sustainable algae-based products.

Partner / country / status: ALGEN / Slovenia / identified and agreed to participate in Webinar on Aquatic systems

Synergy planned: (i) co-operation at events and workshops. (ii) Collaboration in algae valorisation & possible business models establishment.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Europe	CRONUS (Dec 2022 - Aug 2026)	#Aq, #Aq, #BM, #BE	WEB	NTUA	Bio-genic gases, CO2 valorisation, biofuels, sustainable

Project description:

Overall objective is to develop, assess and test 5 new integrated and sustainable technological solutions for highly efficient biogenic effluent gases capture, utilisation, and storage within the biofuels value chain. Functional prototype with algal ponds will capture CO₂ from three processes, including anaerobic digestion, with the help of carbonic anhydrase, extracted from algae, cultivated on digestate.

Partner / country / status: Algen / SLOVENIA / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Cooperation on workshops, (ii) collaborating on potential solutions for rural areas.

Achieved: (i) participation in two national multi-actor innovation workshops

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	BIOEAST Initiative BOOST4BIOEAST (Jan 2024 - Dec 2026)	#For, #BM, #BE	WEB	OMKI	Bioeconomy strategy, research and innovation, rural development

Project description: The Central-Eastern European Initiative for Knowledge-based Agriculture, Aquaculture and Forestry in the Bioeconomy. It provides a common and shared strategic research and innovation framework for working towards sustainable bioeconomies of the Central and Eastern European countries. It is an open initiative started by the Visegrad Group Countries: Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, and joined by Bulgaria, Romania, Slovenia, Croatia and Estonia. The Boost4Bioeast consortium is composed of 30 partners from 17 EU countries (11 BIOEAST countries and Belgium, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Italy and Spain).

Partner / country / status: GEA / ROMANIA / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) visualisation of mutual actions. (ii) Policy recommendations, advocacy. (iii) take part into ERBN

Achieved: (i) Boost4Bioeast Romanian partner and GEA jointly participated in May 2024 in a workshop organised by CEE2ACT on developing the bioeconomy roadmap for Romania, discussed project cooperation areas, (iii) Boost4Bioeast Romanian partners invited to join the ERBN.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	ROSEWOOD 4.0 (Gen 2020-Dec 2022)	#For	WEB	Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum	Network for innovation in forestry

Project description:

Searching, listing and spreading best practices in the wood mobilization sector along with digitalization and innovation all over Europe. The second edition started 01.01.2020-01.01.2021. Created by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. Budget 2.047.901,25E under grant agreement No. 862681.

Partner / country / status: AIEL/ ITALY / finished

Synergy planned: (i) Connect with the existing network in order to get organizations to participate to the BioRural network.

Achieved: The coordinator of the network has been connected but no synergy has been achieved yet.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Alpine Space	Alps4GreenC (Sept 2022-Feb 2024)	#Agr/F; #For; #BE; #BM	WEB	Kemijski inštitut	Biochar production and wooden residues mapping and

Project description:

The Alps4GreenC project is focused on setting-the-scene for transnational utilization of biomass residues through investigation of biomass conversion opportunities in project partner countries and proposal of transnational biochar-based value chains. The framework includes mapping of stakeholders&resources, implementation of crowdsourcing campaign to collect biomass residues and raise awareness, testing and piloting of biochar and context&gap analysis of biomass conversion opportunities for green carbon supply.

Partner / country / status: AIEL/ ITALY / Finished

Synergy planned: co-organisation of events and workshops.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Partner / country / status: UL / Slovenia / Finished

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops; (ii) take part into ERBN; (iii) mutual dissemination.

Achieved: (i) Participation in Alps4GreenC Final Event, (ii) Subscription to ERBN (NIC, National Institute of Chemistry) and (iii) promotion of BioRural events in Slovenia

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
European Joint programme	EJP SOIL - EOM4SOIL (Nov 2021-Oct 2024)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM	WEB	INRAE	Organic matter and soil management

Project description:

EOM4SOIL aims at proposing best management practices of external organic matter (EOM) pre-processing and application on soil to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health. Representative farming systems in Europe (arable crops and vineyards) are selected, taking into account the diversity of pedoclimatic conditions. The net budget of soil C storage and greenhouse gas emission including the pre-process step and field application, is assessed as well as the multiple effects of EOM application on soils including contaminants are quantified. Innovative pre-processing are recommended to improve C budget and soil health. The best management practices are defined from scenarios of use assessed with a multicriteria simulation tool, parameterized from long-term experiments.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / ITALY / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops.

Synergy achieved: (i) co-organisation of three workshops (T3.2) were co-organized with CREA (EJP Soil Italian partner); additionally a 4th workshop by CREA with the methodology designed by BioRural, supported by AIEL (not included in the workshop activities as it was held after the deadline for BioRural).

Partner / country / status: IUNG /Poland / Ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) participation in a workshop organised in Task 3.1.

Synergy achieved: (i) Partners from EJP soil have presented their work at workshop organised within T3.1

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
PRIMA Project	MEDACORNET (Jun 2023 - Jun 2026)	#Ag, #BM	WEB	LANDRATECH	Innovative food products; Product valorisation; rural development

Project description:

The “MEDACORNET” project aims to boost adherence to the Mediterranean diet, through the development of new products based on acorns, as a historic Mediterranean superfood, while promoting the actors involved in its production and processing. The data generated will be used to define dietary guidelines/recommendations and strategies to promote the adoption of acorns as an ingredient in healthy and sustainable Mediterranean diets. In short, MEDACORNET aims to unlock the value chain of the acorn, an ancient traditional ingredient of Mediterranean cuisine produced by several native oak species, currently wasted. Based on the established trans-Mediterranean consortium, the project will produce results in complementary but diversified fields of action, aimed at valuing the acorns of our native forests.

Partner / country / status: CBE / Portugal / discussed

Synergy planned: (i) Potential success story. (ii) Dissemination of results.

Achieved: No further synergy achieved

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HE	genB (Nov 2022 - Apr 2025)	#Hor	WEB	APRE	Young people, teachers, education, awareness, bioeconomy, bio-based, co-creation

Project description:

genB “Preparing tomorrow’s adults to assume their role in a circular and sustainable bioeconomy” aims to prepare children today to assume their role in the future circular and sustainable bioeconomy. In this context, the EU-funded GenB project will involve several other EU projects and initiatives. The project’s overall objective is to inspire and encourage youth and future generations to be aware, sensitive and interested on environmental issues, sustainability and circularity. In cooperation with young people, parents and teachers, GenB will co-create resources like toolkits on bioeconomy and bio-based sectors. To maximise its impacts, GenB will widely engage society, create synergies with other initiatives and consolidate its education model.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / EU / Ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) distribution of EU Challenge call; (ii) other potential synergies to be discussed

Achieved: (i) Distribution of EU Challenge (T3.3) in the SM channels followed by youths community (@biovoices).

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HE	BIOLOC (Oct 2022 – Sept 2025)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM, #BE	https://bioloc.eu/	CEI	biobased, social innovation

Project description: developing resilient innovative biobased activities open to the contribution of socially disadvantaged or marginalized groups. It will deliver innovative and inclusive business models and drive the establishment of permanent public-private multistakeholder hubs to pioneer a social dialogue on innovative and inclusive circular bioeconomy as a leveraging factor for sustainable and resilient local communities.

Partner / country / status: GEA / Romania/ ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Cooperation on workshops, (ii) collaborating on potential solutions for rural areas.

Achieved: (i) participation and promotion of each other’s dissemination actions: Bioloc Romanian partner participated in a conference organized by GEA in October 2023

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
I3	GREET-CE (Nov 2023 – Nov 2025)	#Ag,#BM, #BE	www.greetc.eu	KSENA	regenerative agriculture, eco-construction

Project description: The project focuses on the green transition in Central Europe, aiming to increase the capacity of regional innovation ecosystems, especially SMEs, in less developed Central European regions. The project focuses primarily on green transition within the bioeconomy sector. Key objectives include fostering bioeconomy investments, facilitating interoperation in EU value chains, and enhancing interactive training and education opportunities.

Partner / country / status: GEA / Romania/ agreed and ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Cooperation on workshops, (ii) promoting innovative biobased start-ups

Achieved: (i) co-organized events (ii) promoted BioRural regional challenge workshops announcements in July 2024

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Interreg Europe	ORIGINN (Mar 2023 – May 2027)	#Ag	www.interregeurope.eu/originn	Government of Catalonia	agr-food, industrial innovation, rural areas

Project description: Economic and social transformation in rural areas through industrial innovation, emphasis in agri-food sector. The main goal is to enlarge and improve policy instruments in the involved territories (in EE, ES, IE, IT, RO, SE, SK) seeking to foster innovation-based industrial transition in rural areas, with an emphasis in the agri-food sector. Under this topic, ORIGINN puts special attention to digitalisation, industrial sustainability, social innovation, and soft innovation measures

Partner / country / status: GEA / Romania/ ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Cooperation on workshops, (ii) joint dissemination

Achieved: (i) GEA participated on a workshop organized by OriginN Romanian partner in June 2024.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
LIFE	ConnectHeat (Oct 2022 – Sept 2025)	#BE	WEB	Ambiente Italia S.R.L. (Italy)	district heating, renewable, renewable heat communities

Project description:

ConnectHeat is the first European initiative to develop heating and cooling communities in Europe, implementing seven real pilot cases in different EU countries and putting public authorities and citizens at the heart of energy transitions.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / Italy / participating

Synergy achieved: The partner participated to focus group for the development of renewable heating and cooling communities and the BioRural toolkit was disseminated between the partners.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	BBioNets (Nov 2023 – Oct 2026)	#Ag, #For	WEB	MTU	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

Project description:

BBioNets will rely on, promote, and further advance the work carried out by EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs) with respect to management and/or processing of agricultural and forest biomass with [Bio-Based Technologies \(BBTs\)](#). FANs will identify local needs and, through co-creation and joint actions, prioritise specific BBTs, benefit from and validate knowledge material developed by the consortium building on previous OG and EU-funded project results. Applying the quintuple helix model and a multi-actor approach both within the consortium itself and on the ground activities, BBioNets will set up 6 regional Forest and Agriculture Networks - FANs (IE, EL, ES, IT, PL, CZ) that will ensure balanced representation of all AKIS stakeholders.

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland / participating

Synergy planned: (i) mutual dissemination; (ii) participation in events and workshops,

Achieved: (i) share of newsletter, invitation to workshops ; (ii) Presentation of BioRural toolkit at kickoff meeting of BBioNets

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Interreg	Clim4Cast (03.2023 – 02.2026)	#Ag,	WEB	CZECHGlobe	drought, weather,

Project description: The aim is to increase resilience of the CE region to impacts of drought, heatwaves, fire weather (DHF), and their combined effects, by upgrading existing national tools that mostly ONLY monitor DHF status. The tools will be upgraded by jointly developed DHF forecasts connected to specific action plans on the forecast use and strategy for building DHF-climate change awareness. The project will improve regions' best practises across 7 involved countries but can be scaled up to the entire CE.

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland/ collaboration agreed

Synergy planned: (i) participation in workshops and events

Achieved: (i) Partners from Clim4Cast have presented their work at workshop organised within T3.1

3.3.4 Liaison with National funded projects

Partners have pointed out several national projects which, even not providing directly a EU dimension, also allow connections at country scale and the implementation of relevant synergies. At M12 partners reported a total of 6 national project. At M24 a total of 8 (2 more than at M12) have been identified. From the 17 potential lines of collaboration, a total of 9 synergies occurred by M24.

Table 16. Series to tables to track synergies with National funded projects

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Krajowa Sieć Obszarów Wiejskich +	KSOW+ 2023	#For, #BM, #BE	WEB	Centrum Doradztwa Rolniczego w Brwinowie, Oddział w Warszawie	Rural areas, agriculture

Project description:

The National Rural Network+ (NRN+) is a partnership network for information exchange and cooperation at the regional, national and international level between organizations and administration, representatives of the agricultural sector, advisors, scientists, entities involved in the implementation of innovations and other entities working for the development of agriculture, including increasing its competitiveness and improving the quality of life of inhabitants of rural areas and small towns.

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland / participating

Synergy planned: (i) mutual support in communication; (ii) participation in events, and workshops

Achieved: (i) communication about project achievement, share newsletter, (i) invitation to the NE open call t.3.3

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
German Investing Funding	Bioenergy Initiative Niederbexbach (10/2023 – 10/2028)	#BE		IZES gGmbH (Scientific); Heating grid initiative Niederbexbach (Implementation)	Bioenergy, renewable energy

Project description:

The project was initiated through the citizen of the village Niederbexbach to generate an independence on fossil energy carriers and to develop bio-based solutions for energy supply.

Partner / country / status: IZES gGmbH / Germany / agreed

Synergy planned: Introduction of technologies and project results into toolkit.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
National Project	GrassProtein (2022-2025)	#Ag, #BE	WEB	QPlan	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

Project description:

Increasing perennial forage crop protein yield and increasing biorefining efficiency in order to produce bio economically sustainable livestock feed

Partner / country / status: CERTH / GREECE / identified

Synergy planned: common final event (e.g)

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
EIP Operational Group project	EIP BlueGreen (May 2023 - April 2025)	#BM, #Ag, #Aq	Not yet established	Algen	Food, spirulina, Slovenian farms

Project description:

The project will evolve business model for growing spirulina in Slovenian farms, including logistics, processing and product development in rural areas.

Partner / country / status: Algen / SLOVENIA / agreed and ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) mutual actions and events. (ii) Joint development of business models for farmers growing algae.

Achieved: (i) participation in T3.2 national workshops

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
EIP Operational Group project	InoBerry (2021-2023)	#Agr/F	WEB	VDU	High added value, bio-products, bio-business

Project description:

The main objective of the project is to combine the technological and commercialization processes in order to create products high added value products from the beneficial berry product with the help of an innovative management model.

Partner / country / status: VDU / LITHUANIA/Finished

Synergy planned: (i) involvement into project activities, (ii) introduction of technologies and project results into toolkit.

Achieved: (i) participation in T3.2 national workshop and T1.2. surveys for end-users.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
FEDER funds (FITE – Teruel)	AgriFood-Te (Jan 2023-Dec 2024)	#Ag/F #For, #BM, #BE	WEB	CITA-Te (Centre for innovation in rural bioeconomy of Aragón)	Agriculture, forestry, food, bioenergy, biochemicals

Project description:

AgriFood-Te - AgriFood Knowledge and Innovation Network is financed by the Government of Aragon through the Teruel Investment Fund (FITE). It aims to create a network in the Teruel province, involving more than 100 agents to accelerate exchange scientific knowledge and transfer the results of research and innovation projects to them, and implementing "living-labs" or demonstrative and participatory pilot trials.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / SPAIN / agreed & ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) collaboration in workshops in T3.2; (ii) promotion of participations in EU Challenge

Achieved: (i) co-organising 3 workshops under T3.2 (inland and biobased) in Oct and Nov 2023; (ii) innovative solutions proposed in T3.2 workshops discussed to offer participants to present idea to EU challenge

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
ARIS (CRP)	CircAgro (Oct 2022-Sept 2025)	#Ag/F, #For, #BM, #BE, #Aq	WEB	UL	Agriculture, circular technological concepts business models

Project description:

The general goal of the project is to demonstrate circular system solutions for the use of side streams of biomass from the primary agricultural production to set up convenient and accessible circular business models in tight cooperation and coordination with farms and industry associations involved in project activities. The project focus is on the development of system solutions that will connect agricultural holdings with other actors in supply chains into an innovative circular model for the valorization of biomass side streams on agricultural properties. The model will address the main challenges of the circular use of biomass streams and will have continuous dialogue with policy makers and decision-makers developed proposals for systemic cross-sectoral solution, with a high potential for reproducibility and scalability.

Partner / country / status: UL / Slovenia / Ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) collaboration in national workshops; (ii) promotion of participations in EU Challenge, (iii) success cases; (iv) mutual dissemination

Achieved: (i) co-organising 3 workshops under T3.2; (ii) innovative solutions presented in T3.3 Challenge, (iv) several dissemination of BioRural activities and events

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
EIP Operational Group project	PreConAgri (2023-2025)	#Ag/F, #For, #BM, #BE, #Aq	WEB	CERTH	Agriculture, circular economy

Project description:

The PreConAgri research project is about the application of Conservation and Precision Agriculture techniques to reduce the impact of conventional agricultural practices on climate change through soil carbon sequestration with an increase in soil quality and production. Pilot applications are carried out in model fields of durum wheat, in two Greek regions with severe erosion problems, Krokos Kozanis and Nikaia Larissas. Pilot applications include the implementation of conservation agriculture methodologies, differential fertilization as well as controlled movement of machinery. The results will enhance field sustainability, maximizing benefits for the farmer and the environment

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece / Identified

Synergy planned: (i) joint dissemination activities (ii) promotion of participations in EU Challenge, (iii) success cases;

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

3.4 Liaison with national and EU networks

Liaising with networks and projects is part of BioRural strategy for reaching more impactful results and also to further widen the project reach to diverse stakeholders. In case of networks, these existing collaborative structures, either informal or formal, may have a multiplicative effect for project actions. They may work on themes like bioeconomy, biomaterials, forestry, etc., or may be linked to sectors and then connected with relevant target groups like sectorial companies, practitioners, advisors or scientists.

The liaison is presented below, arranged as next:

- CAP Networks:** both EU and National CAP networks are crucial networks for dissemination and transfer of new biobased solutions. The national eco-systems for knowledge transfer, EIP-Agri operational groups, advisory, etc. are managed or interlinked with CAP networks, and thus a target for BioRural.
- EU Networks:** several identified by M12, though in general scoped to other areas of action with a limited synergy. Only those relevant are being described in the update of D2.1.
- National networks,** which may be theme / actor specific, and may allow for project multiplication or widening its communication and dissemination reach.

3.4.1 EU CAP Network and National CAP Networks

The connection of BioRural with CAP Networks at national level is relevant and strategic, as denoted in D2.1. partners have approached both EU and National CAP networks. At M24 the EU CAP network has already contacted and object of short collaboration on purpose of T1.2. Notwithstanding more contacts are expected in the last stage of the project. In respect the National CAP Networks 9 of them were contacted by M12, now being 2 more totalling 11 out of the 14 BioRural countries. Several synergies took place to disseminate BioRural actions like workshops, through their channels. As well several partners maintain a regular contact, thus allowing mutual transfer of info, more than specific synergies.

Table 17. Series to tables to track synergies with EU and national CAP Networks

Country level	Name	Managed by	LINK	Contact performed / Synergy established
EU	EU CAP Network	European Commission DG AGRI	WEB	CERTH: Not contacted yet. VDU: participated in experts surveys T1.2
ES	Spanish CAP Network keeps the National Rural Network name and website	Ministry of Agric. Fisheries and Food (Spain)	WEB	AVEBIOM: contact to present briefly BioRural. Contact to find synergies in workshops and with new agrarian advisors network. Achieved: dissemination of T3.2 workshops to CAP Network in the agenda of events (Oct & nov 2024)

IT	MASAF – National rural network name and website	Ministry of Agric. Food and Forests	WEB	AIEL: contacted MASAF on purpose of finding synergies.
PT	Portuguese CAP Network keeps the National Rural Network name and website	General Directorate of Agriculture and Rural Development (DGADR)	WEB	CBE: contact to present briefly BioRural.
PL	National Network for Rural Development (Krajowej Sieci Obszarów Wiejskich +)	Krajowa Sieć Obszarów Wiejskich	WEB	IUNG: contacted ERDN on purpose of finding Synergies. Invitation to participate in the workshops and open call
LV	National Rural Network	Latvijas Lauku konsultāciju un izglītības centrs	WEB	LBTU: constant cooperation on many topics Achieved: participation in all T3.1. and T3.2. workshops.
LT	National Rural Network	Ministry of the Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania	WEB	VMU: contacted national NRN on purpose of finding synergies
DK	The Danish Agricultural Agency	Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark	WEB 1 WEB 2	AU: continuously contact as part of public consultancy assignments for the ministry related to the new CAP
DE	DVS Netzwerk Ländliche Räume	Federal Office of Agriculture and Food	WEB	IZES Not contacted yet
NL	Netwerk Platteland	Ministry of Agric. Fisheries and Food (Netherlands)	WEB	DELPHY Not contacted yet
FR	French rural network	ANCT, RDF, French Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty	WEB	VALORIAL already contacted: Achieved: Valorial: contact to present BioRural and strengthen synergies
GR	Greek National CAP	Ministry of Rural Development and Food	WEB	CERTH / FSH Not contacted yet
SL	CAP Network Slovenia	Slovenian Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry & Food	WEB	UL Contacted
RO	National Rural Development Network Romania	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	WEB	GEA: contact to present briefly BioRural and to find synergies in workshops. Achieved: participation in one of the T3.2 workshops in #Ag/F
NMK	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy of the Republic of North Macedonia	Government of the Republic of North Macedonia	WEB	GGP, contact performed Achieved: The Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy is part of the ENRB as one of the country's key stakeholders in the rural bio-economy. Local representatives of this institution took active participation in all of the national capacity building workshops.

Additionally to CAP Networks, the Rural Development Networks of LAGs (Local Action Groups) have been suggested to be approached and incorporated. These contacts form part of country strategies, and reported at country level as part of Section 2.

3.4.2 Liaison with EU relevant networks

The **sectorial clusters and organisations** operating at EU scale are key actors who can support BioRural, and visualise its purpose, program and results towards a wide set of national organisations, and to individual stakeholders in multiple countries. They may be industry driven, private sector based, networks for cooperation and knowledge transfer either public or private, and are relevant for potential multiplicative effects of project actions. At BioRural M24 the status is as next.

Table 18. Series to tables to track synergies with EU sectorial clusters and organisations

ACRONYM	Name / Description	LINK	Contact performed / Synergy established
COPA-COGECA	Farmers and cooperatives EU organisation	WEB	Partner: --- Achieved: ---
Bioenergy Europe (BE)	European association to promote sustainable bioenergy market	WEB	UL & UC contacted and agreed. Achieved: participation into online tutorial T3.1 on bioenergy March 2024. Dissemination of BioRural tutorial to BE members, BE newsletter and social media
ICA	Association for European Life Science Universities	WEB	VDU & AVEBIOM: contacted and agreed Achieved: dissemination of BioRural webinars (T3.1) and EU Challenge Call (T3.3) the EU Challenge through ICA members
ERIAFF	European Regions for Innovation in Agriculture, Food and Forestry	WEB	Valorial: contacted Achieved: participation into 10 th annual conference in June 2024. Dissemination of BioRural project with participants

Additionally to sectorial or theme specific networks, other relevant networks were identified in D2.1 dealing with bioeconomy. The current status of those resulting relevant is as next:

Table 19. Series to tables to track synergies with EU bioeconomy networks

Name / WEB	Description	Contact performed / Synergy established
EPRI European Platform for Rural Innovation / WEB	Open and independent virtual innovation hub to boost bottom up rural development and community-led innovation in rural areas from across the EU.	AVEBIOM: contacted but not active response Achieved: keep insisting from M24
European Bioeconomy Network / WEB	Proactive alliance of 109 EU funded projects and initiatives dealing with Bioeconomy promotion	Partner: --- Achieved: no collaborations achieved so far
European Bioeconomy University / WEB	Alliance of the six leading European universities in this field AgroParisTech, Uni Bologna, Eastern Finland, Hohenheim, BOKU, Wageningen	Partner: --- Achieved: no collaborations achieved so far
Community of Practice for Bioeconomy Education in Europe (ICA-CoP Bio-Edu) / WEB	Committee of the Board of the Association for European Life Science Universities (ICA), to enhance the quality, offer and diversity of education for the sustainable circular bioeconomy in Europe.	AVEBIOM: contacted and discussed. Achieved: invited to distribute info on T3.1 online tutorials (Nov 2023); invited to participate in T3.3 EU Challenge AVEBIOM/VDU: contacted and discussed. Achieved: widespread T3.3 EU Challenge call to ICA members to reach lecturers and students.
European Bioeconomy Alliance / WEB	Informal alliance of leading European organisations active in the bioeconomy. BIC, CEFS, CEPF, CEPI, COPA-COGECA, ePURE, EuropaBio, EUBP, FEDIOL, FTP, PFP, Starch Europe	Partner: --- Achieved: no collaborations achieved so far
Biorefine Cluster Europe / WEB	The Biorefine Cluster Europe interconnects projects and people within the domain of biobased resource recovery, striving to contribute to a more sustainable resource management.	AVEBIOM: contacted and discussed. Achieved: motivated meeting with CERTH to find synergies RBA and BioRural with Biorefine. Potential learning of their value proposition to preserve BioRural toolkit
ERDN - European Rural Development Network / WEB	It integrates efforts and competences of various EU research institutions for transformation of rural areas, in particular farming. It aims to build a EU Research Area for agriculture and rural development.	AVEBIOM: contacted and discussed. Achieved: widespread T3.3 EU Challenge call to ERDN members, principally scientists and lecturers who could trigger new applications with students. IUNG: constant contact and sharing information about project Achieved: ERDN presentation at workshop organised in T3.1, acceptance to participate in their conference sept 2024
CIGR Bioeconomy Network WEB	Create a network for Agricultural Biosystems Engineering professionals and related disciplines to collaborate to develop and disseminate useful knowledge and technology related to circular bioeconomy that leads to improved quality of life of all in a sustainable and socially responsible manner.	AU: Member of network Achieved: Participation in regular meetings.

3.4.3 Liaison with National networks

National networks have been identified in National Engagement plans developed by partners (see in D2.1 annex of national plans). At M12 partners reported a total of 16 national networks as being relevant for project implementation at country level. Having already 8 ongoing contacts and discussions and having reached 3 agreements for collaboration. At M24 partners have identified a total of 21, five more than at M12. From the total 23 synergies discussed already at this stage, a total of 20 individual collaborations have been triggered with 15 of these networks.

Table 20. Series to tables to track synergies with National networks

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Spain (National)	INtercamBIOM	AVEBIOM, CIRCE	WEB	Biomass resources, bioenergy, bioproducts
<p>Network description: INtercamBIOM network is a National Thematic Network through which participants can easily and directly keep up to date with INNOVATIVE PRACTICES that are already being applied in the field of biomass supply, bioenergy and value-added uses. INtercamBIOM has been implemented in the framework of the BRANCHES Horizon 2020 project (Grant Agreement no. 101.000375).</p> <p>Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / SPAIN / agreed</p> <p>Synergy planned: (i) mutual transfer of case studies and success cases. (ii) Invitation to form part of BioRural</p> <p>Achieved: (i) two success cases of INtercamBIOM adapted and uploaded into BioRural; (i) agreed to disseminate T2.3 & T2.4 success cases into INtercamBIOM; (ii) communication to INtercamBIOM network about ERBN and subscription</p>				
Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Lithuania (Sub-national)	AKIS Cluster	VDU	WEB	Knowledge transfer, partnerships, agriculture
<p>Network description: It is an ecosystem of advanced organizations gathered on a voluntary initiative, the operation of which is based on coordinated, partnership and networked knowledge flows between individuals, organizations and institutions that create and implement knowledge and innovations for agriculture and related sectors in order to achieve progress, sustainability and competitiveness in the sector.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: VDU/ Lithuania/ agreed</p> <p>Synergy planned: continuous communication. As well potential collaboration in workshops and events.</p> <p>Achieved: (i) participation in T3.2 national workshop and (ii) T1.2. surveys for end-users.</p>				
Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Poland (National)	Agroekoton Association	Agroekoton	WEB	Agriculture, Horticulture,
<p>Network description: Organisation focuses on the intersections between different agriculture-related communities, connecting scientists, growers, consumers, local governments, industry organisations, and many others. We aim to facilitate the exchange of ideas and to create real value, both for those communities and for the environment. AGROEKOTON is a place for creating new ideas and adapting them for use in agriculture, according to European Union strategies.. Our core values are commitment, cooperation, and innovation.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland</p> <p>Synergy planned: participation in events, and workshops</p> <p>Achieved: ongoing communication, preparation of join project proposal, participation in Conference co-organised by AGROECOTON IBO SUMMIT 2023</p>				
Poland (Sub-national)	LODR	LODR	WEB	Agriculture, food, bioenergy,
<p>Network description: Deals with consulting in the field of agriculture, rural development, agricultural markets and rural households, aimed at improving the level of income from agriculture and improving the market competitiveness of farms, supporting sustainable development of rural areas and raising the level of professional qualifications of farmers and other rural residents.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland</p> <p>Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops, surveys, dissemination</p>				

Achieved: ongoing communication, preparation of joint projects proposals, promotion of workshops organised by BioRural between farmer and advisors

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Germany (Sub-national)	Biosphärenzweckverband	Administration for organisation of biosphere reserve	WEB	Agriculture, forestry, food, bioenergy, biomaterials, local producer, sustainability
<p>Network description: Network of rural bioeconomic actors, local producer of bio-based (nutrition) products and biomaterials. Principle: Think global, act local. Regional awareness for global environmental protection.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: IZES / Germany / in discussion</p> <p>Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops</p> <p>Achieved: no synergies achieved so far</p>				

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Danish	Food & Bio Cluster	Governing Body	WEB	Agriculture, forestry, food, bioenergy, biochemicals
<p>Network description: Denmark's national cluster organisation for the Danish food and bioresource industry. It is a unifying platform for innovation and growth – for Danish and international companies and knowledge institutions. Food & Bio Cluster Denmark exists to strengthen knowledge-based innovation and collaboration between companies and knowledge institutions across the food and bioresources value chain. We are the gateway to networking, the development of new business ideas and funding opportunities. Food & Bio Cluster Denmark has over 300 Danish and international members, including startups, established companies, knowledge institutions, municipalities, regional authorities and other public institutions.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: AU / Denmark / identified</p> <p>Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops</p> <p>Achieved: Co-organizer of two out of three national workshops (T3.3) in Denmark. Provided input for innovation ideas discussed at the workshops.</p>				
Danish	CBIO (Aarhus University Centre for Circular Bioeconomy)	Governing Body	WEB	Agriculture, forestry, food, bioenergy, biochemicals
<p>Network description: CBIO activities include research within the entire production chain ranging from cultivating and procuring biomasses, logistics, management, refining, product development and tests, recirculation, impact on nature and environment as well as research in relation to society and economy. In addition, more basic research activities are carried out, e.g. in relation to the understanding of biomass conversion at molecular level, supported by advanced chemical analyses.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: AU / Denmark / identified</p> <p>Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops and other dissemination activities, building networks, etc.</p> <p>Achieved: Participated in national workshop in Denmark. Provided input for the innovation idea on protein extraction discussed in the workshop.</p>				

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
The Netherlands (National)	Building Balance	Network governing body	WEB	Biobased solution, construction industry
<p>Network description: Building Balance aims to boost the bioeconomy through the development of new value chains around sustainable construction materials.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: Delphy / The Netherlands / agreed</p> <p>Synergy planned: (i) mutual transfer of case studies and success cases. (ii) Visualisation of mutual actions. (iii) Potential workshop on inland resources.</p> <p>Achieved: (iii) Participated in national workshop in the Netherlands. (ii) Delphy participates in various consultation groups within Building Balance to provide expert advice</p>				

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
France (regional)	CIVAM network	CIVAM	WEB	Agriculture, food, Biomass resources
<p>Network description: Driven by strong values of humanism and cooperation, the CIVAM network brings together farmers, association leaders and citizens in Normandy who want to support the development of sustainable farming and food systems and an environmental approach to behaviour.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: NaturePlast/ FRANCE/ identified Synergy planned: Share network and pool the effects. Achieved: Initial discussions were held with members of this network to promote BioRural and present the toolkit.</p>				
France (regional)	Pays de la Loire Hub for Bioeconomy	Pays de la Loire region	WEB	Biomass resources and circular economy
<p>Network description: The aim of the Bioeconomy Hub is to create a collective dynamic in Pays de la Loire that will enable the emergence of European projects. Its aim is to take greater account of the interests of the region's players in the circular bioeconomy value chain.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE/ agreed Synergy planned: co-organisation of events and workshops. Achieved: Agreement to disseminate BioRural events and actions</p>				
France (regional)	NFA Normandie Filière Algues	Normandie	Web	Seaweed, algoculture and creation of
<p>Network description: Bringing together seaweed stakeholders in Normandy to structure and develop the development of seaweed resources</p> <p>Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE/ contacted Synergy planned: to be discussed Achieved: no synergy achieved so far</p>				
France (regional)	Réseau NOÉ Bretagne	Brittany	WEB	Research and innovation
<p>Network description: Since 2008, the Noé Bretagne network has brought together the main academic and socio-economic players in Brittany involved in research and innovation.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE/ agreed Synergy planned: mutual dissemination Achieved: assistance for implementation of action and dissemination at regional level.</p>				

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Romania (National)	Local Action Groups for Fisheries – FLAGs	FLAG	WEB	Fishery
<p>Network description: Romanian National Fisheries Network, to support Local Action Groups in fishing areas (FLAGs) in their efforts to contribute to the sustainable development of fishing areas included in the Local Development Strategies. The National Fisheries Network plays an important role in the connection and cooperation of FLAGs, all actors and authorities involved in the development of the fisheries sector. The National Fishing Network also participates in geographical and thematic groups for the development of activities, the promotion of more extensive cooperation, the promotion of technical exchange and dialogue between networks.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: GEA / ROMANIA / identified Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops Achieved: collaborated with FLAG Galati branch in organising a workshop on aquaculture in March 2024.</p>				
Romania (Sub-National)	ECORURALIS Association	ECORURALIS	WEB	Agriculture, food, short value chain, farm-to-fork
<p>Network description: Association of farmers and peasants, which operates at the national level, with almost 20,000 members in all counties of the country. The association was founded in 2009 and represents the interests and rights of peasants, small producers and people working in the countryside in Romania.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: GEA / ROMANIA / in discussion Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops Achieved: no synergies achieved so far</p>				
Romania (Sub-National)	Romanian Forestry Association	ASFOR	WEB	forestry

Network description: ASFOR is a professional organization, autonomous, non-governmental and apolitical, of economic agents in the primary wood exploitation and processing industry, representing, supporting and defending their economic, technical, commercial and social interests in relations with public authorities, trade unions and other legal and natural persons, nationally and internationally.

Partner / country / status: GEA / ROMANIA / in discussion

Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops

Achieved: (i) collaborated in promoting and organising workshop on forestry in November 2023, (ii) jointly participated in a workshop organised by CEE2ACT project, coordinator of the National Bioeconomy Hub, in May 2024, with the topic: consultation with stakeholders to develop a roadmap for the bioeconomy in Romania.

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Slovenia (National)	SRIP circular economy	Algen, UL	WEB	Biomass resources, bioenergy, bioproducts, circular economy

Network description:

The Strategic Research and Innovation Partnership – Networks for the transition into circular economy (SRIP – Circular economy) is a connection of Slovenian business subjects, educational and research institutions (RRI), non-governmental organisations and other interested parties, in collaboration with the state, into new value chains according to the economic principles of closed material flows.

Partner / country / status: Algen / Slovenia / Interested

Synergy planned: Mutual transfer of case studies and success cases. Invitation to be a part of BioRural – agreed.

Achieved: Collaborated in promoting online Knowledge Exchange Workshops

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
IT	ICHAR - Italian Association of Biochar producers	CNR	WEB	Biochar, biomaterials

Network description:

Ichar is the Italian Biochar Association that promote demonstration activities in support of Biochar (vegetable carbon) and its diffusion, through educational tools and projects related to its production and use.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / ITALY / identified

Synergy planned: co-organisation of events and workshops.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

IT	Italia Solare	Italia Solare	WEB	Renewable energy
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Network description:

ITALIA SOLARE is a third sector association that supports the defense of the environment and human health by supporting intelligent and sustainable methods of production, storage, management, and distribution of energy through distributed generation from renewable sources, in particular photovoltaics.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / ITALY / identified

Synergy planned: co-organisation of events and workshops.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

IT	PescAgri	CIA	WEB	Aquaculture
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Network description:

PescAgri is the Italian Fishermen's Association promoted by CIA for the protection, development and enhancement of fishing and aquaculture in all its professional and territorial meanings.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / ITALY / identified

Synergy planned: co-organisation of events and workshops.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
PT	SPM	SPM	WEB	Biomaterials

Network description:

Portuguese Society of Materials (SPM) aims to bring together individuals and legal entities interested in promoting, at a national level, the improvement, development and progress of Materials Science and Technology. It seeks to be the voice of Materials in Portugal and take the lead in discussion and interconnection with political and economic decision-makers, academia, business and civil society.

Partner / country / status: CBE/UC / Portugal / Agreed
Synergy planned: co-organization of events and workshops.
Achieved: Joint organisation of Bio-based industries and services workshop in Portugal.

PT	ASWP	ASWP	WEB	Residues Valorisation, Circular economy
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Network description:
 SmartWaste Portugal (ASWP) is a non-profit association whose mission is to enhance the Circular Economy in the various value chains, through education, innovation, collaboration and the creation of new businesses. It intends to establish itself as a hub that brings together and aggregates interests, with a focused perspective for the business.

Partner / country / status: CBE/UC / Portugal / Agreed
Synergy planned: Participation in common events and projects. Dissemination of actions.
Achieved: Dissemination and participation by ASWP in the Bio-based industries and services workshop in Portugal.

4 Area of action #3: establishing a durable ERBN structure

4.1 Introduction

The third Area of action for the ERBN strategy is the **creation of a structure of organisations to take over the management of the network after BioRural finishes**. For this purpose, it is necessary to set a strategy for the network that generates sufficient value and interest for the network members, but as well to the network managers. Otherwise, the management structure may not count with the necessary strength and initiative to keep it alive.

The principal values that the ERBN may inherently include were described in D2.1, section 1.3). In summary the value is the aggregation of key actors and stakeholders interested in small-scale biobased solutions for the bioeconomy progress in rural areas. The value increases as far as the network is well populated, but as well as it is active: members invite other stakeholders to join, there is a traffic of contacts, demands for services, and growing trend in the volume of materials (bio-based solutions, success cases, etc.) available in the toolkit, which are being facilitated by these ERBN members, not by the managerial structure of by BioRural partners. Another value derives from a potential recognition by national AKIS managers as a relevant platform, and if it becomes connected to official acknowledged platforms like EIP-Agri or EU-Farmbook.

4.2 Actions and status at M24

In order to build such a management structure for the ERBN D2.1 included a plan of actions to take place from M12 onwards (available in D2.1 section 4.3). This plan from M12 – M24 included next items:

1. Approach potential key organisations to become part of ERBN managerial structure and create first core board
2. Define ERBN scope and basic action lines (ERBN definition, mission, potential tasks, working groups)
3. Draft planning of actions and identification of resources to maintain operative the toolkit

The status is reported in next sub-chapters.

4.2.1 Key actors and Managerial structure

At month M12, August 2023, a total of 230 persons were already part of the ERBN, among them 182 from key partners organisations. If counting BioRural partners, who are key actors, at least during project action, it added 252 members. At the current status M24, BioRural project has achieved to incorporate to the ERBN 472 persons, among which 338 are affiliated in key actors organisations.

From M12 till M24, as explained in Section 2, the engagement has pursued to consolidate the trust and interest of pre-aware key actors, and to further proceed to identify and start awareness raising with those who had not been contacted. At M12 a total of 78 key actors had already collaborated and supported project, a figure that evolved positively till M24 to reach 229 key actors collaborating with BioRural (151 more than at M12).

In this period partners have identified which, among these key actors, could go further and start cooperating in ERBN structure and core board. In order to coordinate such identification, two initial internal meetings took place with all partners in October 2023 (during the consortium meeting in Rome) and Dezember 2023 (4th Dezember, online). The intend was to work towards the construction of a core committee, but next issues arose when planning its practical implementation.

Issue 1: organisations ready to lead ERBN board, RBP boards and National boards

At M12 it was proposed the core board would have to integrate several organisations, from different countries (see Figure 23). It was proposed a structure by geographical nodes, with a representative per RBP in the ERBN board (the highest decision making body, depicted in green at the top in Figure 23). Furthermore, a group of regional sub-boards for each RBP (NW, NE, SW, SE) would operate in a second hierarchical level, as depicted in red in Figure 23.

A third level for management would consist on national boards, one per country, with a leader (participating in the RBP Board) and other complementary organisations (from R&D, sector, AKIS management bodies, etc.)

Figure 23. Proposal of internal structure of governance for the ERBN as presented at M12

The discussions held during M14 till M16 showed that from BioRural partners: 3 of them declared positively to be ready to lead National and RBP Boards. Among the rest other 5 countries would count with a BioRural partner interested to be national leader in the National board, though they would need first to count with other backup or support from national key organisations (in ministries, AKIS managers, etc.). Among the rest of countries 4 of them would count with a BioRural partner interested to be part of the National boards, but not to lead.

In respect external organisations (different from BioRural partners), it was found that at that moment no one had declared interest to manage ERBN as main national coordination point. BioRural partners suggested a list of potential key organisations who could take this role, built probably with a secondary role, not as the referential organisation at national level. It was argued ministries (sDG, or departments) are too much high level and companies would not be appropriate national leaders. More appropriate would be R&D large organisations or national innovation bioeconomy hubs or bioeconomy networks, as these organisations can find into ERBN a path for growth, as being very aligned with its own purposes, and also a facilitating connections and value.

Issue 2: theme specific is a main value

It was evidenced in the discussions that the main new value of ERBN was the specificity by subject: small-rural-biobased-innovative-solutions and its arrangement in five thematic areas on resources (agri-food, forestry, aquatic) and path for deployment (bioenergy and biomaterials/bioproducts). This was in coherence with D2.1 value described in its Section 1.3.

Beyond of this value, the challenges and risks identified in section 4.2 (see tables 18 and 19) also indicated that specificity was needed to be a pivotal point for ERBN, as for example:

- To count with a definition of the ERBN to state clear the areas of action, and to avoid becoming too broad and unspecific
- To develop a 3 or 4 year plan with main objectives and actions foreseen, to keep aligned the interest of all countries. Otherwise the different regions or countries could dissalign from the scope of network

During the internal meeting on 4th Dezember 2023 it was argued if the geographical managerial structure arranged by geographical areas (as in Figure 23) would be operative. As observed it foresaw a three-level managerial

structure. But then the thematic connection would be through other collaborative pats. For example in working groups. This would add more representatives in the top management board of the ERBN (see Figure 23, depicted on the right side, in yellowish colour).

BioRural partners agreed the structure could be simplified by means of a managerial structure well connected to topics, but still allowing for synergy creation in regional actions (specially to coordinate between neighbouring countries and to facilitate more cross-border cooperation). This structure was drafted and shared with all partners after the meeting, as presented next in Figure 24.

Figure 24. Proposal of internal structure of governance for the ERBN as presented at M12

As observed the managerial structure reduces a layer. It also allows the integration of key actors in specific thematic board (depicted blue in Figure 24), or as the thematic leader into ERBN board (depicted green in Figure 24). This provides a unique value, as these organisations are acknowledged as referential by theme, which is a value (outside ERBN they are envisioned as the key organisations on a specific theme). This value was not allowed with the original distribution (in Figure 23) by geographical. As observed geographical coordination would be habilitated by means of regional coordination groups (RBPs) who could have a representative in the Principal ERBN board (presented yellowish on the right side of Figure 24).

Re-scoping the planning to for the ERBN (according to Issue 1 and 2)

As presented above, under Issue 1 and 2, the consideration of ERBN as thematic driven diverges from the initial envisioning proposed in D2.1 by M12. This affects ERBN definition, and the profile of actors who could be part of the structure. Furthermore it affects the communications to be carried to targeted key actors to take part into ERBN, as it requires a re-definition.

From M16 onwards AVEBIOM worked with CERTH, VDU and other partners in the preparation of a new definition for ERBN. Furthermore, the ERBN status evaluated at M18 (mid-project report) evidenced that the interactions were still limited. And that to engage key actors to be part of the managerial structure, it would be welcomed to further evolved and upgrade the contents in the toolkit.

4.2.2 ERBN scope and steps followed till M24

The re-scoping for ERBN was addressed in a first stage by CERTH and AVEBIOM as project coordinator and as responsible of WP2 respectively. As result of the conversations a very simple SWOT matrix was built. It was specially relevant for the re-orientation of the ERBN scope. The main lines of the SWOT are presented in Table 20.

Table 21. SWOT analysis on the re-scoping of ERBN towards thematic division and post-project continuity

Strengths	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several partners are theme specific (agrifood, or bioenergy, or biomaterials, etc.) and are more prone to take leadership if ERBN is thematic • Multiple partners have experience in EU network and project participation • BioRural is part of RBA and is able to engage RBA project coordinators to grow-up the ERBN • ERBN and RBA have both a brand are become being known 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The themes, technologies and success cases in toolkit are selected by partners and not under demand (e.g. from primary sector needs) • ERBN and BioRural toolkit are currently standalone, not linked to any official platform or EU instrument • Ability to engage national AKIS bodies for most of partners (potential involvement is not easy) • Project partners are not representative of primary producers • After project ends viability is not possible without funding or strong role from ERBN board • The current behaviour of most ERBN members is passive (no action after subscription)
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge in primary sector on bio-based solutions (they demand knowledge to comply with Green Deal) • Funding opportunities for new bioeconomy networks • EU-Farmbook in initial stage, potential connection with ERBN and BioRural toolkit • modernAKIS initiatives as a path to reinforce connections of ERBN with national AKIS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New structure may require more funding or may involve actions not planned under BioRural • To not achieve engagement of sufficient actors on-time • To diverge too much from original scope and cause distrust into current ERBN members • To not achieve integration with existing referential platforms (EU-Farmbook and others) • More networks and projects proceed, possibility to become buffered

As result of this analysis it was envisioned several action lines to re-orientate the strategy, as presented next in Table 22.

Table 22. Strategic actions as derived from SWOT analysis

Strategy	Actions to be included in a thematic ERBN network
Re-define the ERBN	The ERBN could be re-defined as: multi-actor (MA) thematic network (TN) for knowledge sharing on innovative solutions for sustainable circular bioeconomy (CB) applicable by farmers and foresters (practitioners) at a local scale in rural areas to cover their most urgent needs on the management of biological by-products and residues
Respond to primary producers urgent needs	Actions to consult most urgent needs on the management of biological by-products and residues, to later on identify existing solutions either from EU projects, Operational Groups or grassroots from primary sector. This could include surveys, participative workshops, or direct contacts. And identification of areas or regions requiring urgent solutions.
Offer information more suitable to primary sector	The current toolkit already facilitate simple information, and available in 14 languages. Short summaries on success cases and technologies are available. They could be complemented with testimonials, not necessarily highly edited videos or interviews, but more practical and from the voice of user.
Involve RBA projects strongly into ERBN	The collaboration under RBA is being fruitful in terms of supporting the RBA projects communication and dissemination. However, to fully take advantage from the materials, community and tools developed by these projects, it is necessary an agreement for further cooperation with ERBN and toolkit
Connect to EU-Farmbook	EU-Farmbook is the EU-wide interactive knowledge reservoir called to be a dissemination channel most consulted by farmers and foresters with automatic translation services. To be linked to EU-Farmbook it is necessary to interconnect EU-Farmbook knowledge platform with BioRural toolkit. And to offer complementary information in BioRural toolkit. This requires a negotiation with EU-Farmbook coordinator and dissemination leaders.
Connect to AKIS	To achieve this it requires ERBN representatives at national level to have a good contact and interaction with national AKIS bodies. The interaction with modernAKIS is a good path. But also it would be advisable to participate into SCAR strategic working groups on bioeconomy

	and on AKIS. This requires ERBN representatives to take this role. But also would be required to have lessons learned and policy recommendations prepared, to be conveyed to these groups.
Widen the ERBN reach	At the moment the members into ERBN have been engaged by direct communications, though also multiple enrolled freely after becoming aware. To further widen the ERBN it could offer to host the communities of practice and knowledge exchange created in EU projects like RBA projects or through Operational Groups. This requires revision of the procedures for affiliation to ERBN through the BioRural toolkit
ERBN branding should prevail above BioRural	During BioRural life time BioRural toolkit and BioRural actions have reached a good branding in the participating countries but as well at EU level. However after project the remaining brand will be the ERBN, and therefore the actions will be rebranded. A transition is necessary already during BioRural lifetime
Connection with other EU institutions and programs	Connection with EU CAP Network is fundamental. Participation in working groups or workshops would be part of ERBN board and working group members. It may facilitate also the transfer of knowledge as well as of recommendations or urgent needs. Interactions with DG Agri would be also a key action line to make ERBN instrumental for Europe.
Activate and keep offering value to ERBN members	First 24 months for BioRural have evidenced a limited interaction between ERBN members (at least to the extent the toolkit platform allows to track). Potential actions have been proposed in M18 project report. They would contribute to the knowledge transfer and also to connect offer-and-demand (providers of solutions with practitioners). The ERBN should include actions to promote interaction, as well as to become a channel to communicate news of interest beyond the BioRural newsletter.

4.2.3 Planning for ERBN and identification of resources

Given the changes in the scoping of ERBN that took place by M16, it was advisable to stop the engagement of actors to create a first core of ERBN managerial structure. This core group, according to the planning foreseen at M12 (as reflected in D2.1) would have to meet and develop a first draft program of actions (to start after project end). However, under the re-orientation of the ERBN, it was not possible to create such first core group.

Following the strategic lines as presented in Table 22, the actions performed from M13 till M24 have concentrated in the connection with EU-Farmbook by CERTH and AVEBIOM. IUNG as responsible of toolkit has collaborated to identify potential actions to connect with EU-Farmbook. VDU contributed to the EU scope and connections with SCAR or EIP Agri. Valorial and GEA suggested forms of connection with other innovation clusters, with primary producers and the integration of local communities.

All partners have discussed about the potential activation of the ERBN members has been object of discussion with all partners in M22 thus gathering ideas like: publish an agenda, facilitate the publication of demands for service or support, deployment of webinars or workshop to capture urgent needs, utilise the ERBN to support the ideas selected under the EU Challenge from M25 onwards.

Furthermore, sources for funding have been detected, like the HE calls for cluster 6 2023-2024 program like Thematic Networks or CirBio (though they are specific for themes like textile, forests, etc.). As well at national level partners have been encouraged to identify sources which could complement ERBN maintenance and upgrade, as could be Operational Groups as a path for specific transfer from toolkit. Programs like HE CBE JU 2024 calls have been revised as well, not having any call for a similar knowledge structure maintenance, as ERBN would require

4.3 Actions beyond M24

A first step needed is rebranding of toolkit and part of the web, to be more evident ERBN. This will be handled in M25 during the General Assembly meeting. Another early step will be the activation of ERBN members. It has been ideated to do it in connection with BioRural tasks, as for example T3.3, in order to call for collaboration with the ideas presented in each RBP to the BioRural EU challenge.

Additional efforts will be placed for collaboration with BioRural sister projects and RBA projects, to connect more strongly to ERBN and BioRural toolkit (ERBN platform). During autumn- winter 2024 to 2025 a core of organisations from BioRural, together with other non-partner organisations will be engaged to create a core group, to start implementation of actions as presented in Table 22. By M30 an operational plan and the funding (if necessary) must have been identified. From then onwards the ERBN core and action plan could be released. And start operation during or after project will be decided.

5 Conclusions

BioRural partners have performed actions of engagement to activate key actors who have been identified as relevant to implement BioRural actions, to widen its impact, or to build the ERBN structure. By M12 (August 2023) partners developed a national strategic plan by identifying key actors necessary, which were appendix to D2.1. All partners organised initial contacts to raise awareness and interest in the targeted key actors, in order to activate them, and to make them to participate and collaborate with the project. Partners did also perform liaison actions to connect BioRural with other projects and networks, in order to create synergies and connect the project to relevant structures or networks of targeted actors. The summary of these actions, by M12 is presented in the previous Deliverable report D2.1.

The present deliverable is a follow-up of D2.1, and preserves a similar structure. From M13 until M24 partners have executed multiple actions of impact, like workshops, online tutorials and multiple events and presentations. Furthermore, partners have continued engaging key actors to subscribe into the ERBN community, and started contacts with national key actors to collaborate and continue with the maintenance of the ERBN.

The main result of partners efforts under T2.1 and T2.2 to engage key actors and to liaise with projects and networks is presented next:

- 1,131 key actors have been identified in total, 244 more than those identified at M12. Among them 824 have been engaged thanks to direct communications and meetings. The engagement has led by M24 to add in total 356 key actors participating in BioRural actions, and 229 having also supported BioRural actions or co-organised BioRural events.
 - ➔ The progress with respect the achievements by M12 is remarkable, with additional 190 key actors participating and 151 key actors collaborating
- A cluster of 11 EU-funded bioeconomy projects (the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance) has been created, launched, communication channels created, and EU collaboration started. At national level BioRural partners have achieved 29 individual collaborations
 - ➔ In respect M12, synergies have taken place. The initially discussed 11 lines of collaboration, that have widened to 37 by M24. Multiple have been achieved, thus leading to 29 individual collaborations
- A total of 32 EU (24) and national (8) projects have been identified to be very relevant for BioRural, leading to 29 collaborations taking place
 - ➔ The progress with respect the achievements by M12 is high, since ta that moment the synergies had been discussed or were under planning.
- The EU CAP Network has been identified as crucial to link BioRural actions and impacts, and contacts established in 11 out of the 14 BioRural countries
 - ➔ In respect M12, an additional national CAP network has been contacted. Furthermore the EU CAP Network has been approached and started short collaboration. Several partners have achieved to disseminate BioRural actions through national CAP networks, and made representatives to participate in BioRural actions.
- A total of 33 EU (12) and national (21) networks have been identified as relevant for establishing connections for knowledge transfer. Achieving 29 individual collaborations, with 5 EU referential networks (8 collaborations) and 15 national networks (21 collaborations)
 - ➔ The progress with respect the achievements by M12 is an expansion from 24 to 33 identified networks, and the achievement of collaborations in practice.

- The ERBN community counts already with 472 members, among them 338 being affiliated to the identified key actors. The ERBN network value, challenges, risks and mission has been discussed, and a plan for growing it up and to create the internal structure has been prepared
 - ➔ The progress with respect the achievements by M12 is good, with a progress of additional 220 members
- The ERBN governance structure has been revised and re-scoped, to make ERBN more similar to a thematic network, rather than a group of regional clusters, as it was foreseen by M12. All partners have participated in the discussions, and strategic lines have been prepared by AVEBIOM and CERTH.
 - ➔ The progress with respect M12 is principally the re-scoping of the ERBN and the first contacts to connect to relevant Eu platforms like EU-Farmbook.

At the current status the challenge for the next period is to keep the engagement towards effective collaborations with key actors, projects and networks, specially to transfer and communicate BioRural results. Furthermore the liaison with key actors is expected to lead to an effective collaboration to maintain the ERBN after BioRural finishes. It is expected as well a re-dynamisation of the ERBN community, and a more strong connection to other EU projects, and therefore a relevant growth in the ERBN is expected, as well as an activation of the behaviour of members.

Appendix

ANNEX 1 - Country updates at M24

This annex to D2.2 deliverable report contains the individual updates for these 14 countries at the date of M24 (August 2024).

Link to report: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ETTEc65IP8hMDvSlKD1j_P-KFNlgWY-b/view?usp=drive_link